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Executive Summary

This document reports about the activities and results of case study 1 CS1 (task T5.1) “Case study on training”, which aims (i) at testing whether the NANORIGO risk governance framework (NRGF) can improve training towards safe working practices and particularly in nanorisk governance, and (ii) at demonstrating the usefulness of the NRGF for preparing the training by trainers. This includes the NRGF process and the associated NANORIGO Web-platform developed by WP3. In this context PLUS set up a training program on deeper understanding and practical application of the NRGF, including working safely with nanomaterials (NM) with respect to hazard and exposure as well as to accountability and responsibility. UL supported in providing training material, takeover of a training lecture, and compilation of a reflection on the created training program.

PLUS, thus, organized trainings for early career scientists and students at two different training sites, Salzburg and Venice with subsequent survey of attendees and experts for evaluation and monitoring of the NRGF’s functionality in assisting their distinct roles as (i) scientists targeted for the training and as (ii) trainers.

The training programs as well as most associated training resources were made available open access under CC BY 4.0 license using formats including the OpenAIRE Zenodo platform and the YouTube channel of the EU NanoSafety Cluster. The training program will be available beyond the lifetime of the project.

The analysis of the gathered survey data provides strong evidence that the NANORIGO NRGF, including the NANORIGO Web-platform, represented a beneficial resource collection (data, tools, information) to support knowledge acquisition and enhancement of the understanding of a best practice approach of risk governance, going beyond conventional risk assessment and covering the whole life cycle of risk.

A strong coherence was affirmed in regard to (i) the most pressing needs for trainers, which – by voting – had been identified as (1) the availability of a handy risk governance process description, (2) a user-friendly guidance through the framework and (3) the availability of e-learning content and an easy to locate access point and (ii) corresponding beneficial features of the NRGF resource collection and NANORIG’s ready to use training material. About 40% of survey participants (training providers) confirmed that they have already checked out the NANORIGO NRGF and the NANORIGO portal and concluded, that for training of nanorisk governance the most important and beneficial steps are step 1, pre-assessment and step 4, evaluation. Step 2, scientific assessment, and step 5, management, are deemed to be very context-dependent, thus training has to be customized anyway and trainers’ expectations concerning beneficial effects of tailored NRGF content are not that high.

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The feedback of early career researchers exceeded the overall positive impression of the trainers. 90% of early career researchers classified the NRGF proposed process as strongly supportive or at least moderately supportive, with emphasis on strong support. The most important elements of the risk governance framework for early career researchers are (1) the “e-learning content” and (2) the “user-friendly guidance”, “data collections” and “tool collections”. To sum up, young scientists, involved in the educational event and role play, centered around the case of the EU commission “TiO₂ food ban”, expressed very strong conviction that applying the NANORIGO NRGF would have been beneficial for better decision making.

Overall, the outcome of the case study CS1 provides evidence for the applicability and utility of the NANORIGO NRGF for the CS's defined target groups.

1. Introduction

This document is the Deliverable **D5.2 Report on case study on training** which has been developed as part of the NANORIGO (NANOtechnology Risk GOVERNance) project. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, under the grant number 814530. This Deliverable has been developed under Task 5.1: **Case study on training** of Work Package 5: Demonstration of sustainable solution (case studies).

The use of the NRGF will require training, both to understand its concepts and to make use of its tools. Acceptance of the NRGF, thus, rests strictly on the availability of training materials that make it easy for users to become familiar with NRGF to the level they need. The persons to be trained will be from very different groups, for example senior and junior scientists, workers, decision makers and media experts. The NRGF will, from a technical perspective, in principle be quite simple, in practice, however, it will be very complex in order to deal with a wide variety of issues. Therefore, the question arose: What is in this situation the best way to set up training programs?

Contribution of CS1 to NRGF is *via* checking for completeness of all information in the whole nanorisk governance process represented by the NRGF framework and portal, thus, performing a gap analysis, from the perspective of trainers and trainees. A specific contribution is towards opinion and concern assessment, since, for this step, it is necessary to inform various parties on NRGF procedures and to communicate outcomes of processes to all stakeholders. Training providers and, more broadly, information providers, will be able to use elements of this and future training programs.

The stakeholders represented here are training providers that want to offer training for NRGF users. That can include consultants and SMEs specialized in training, large industry that needs to train and re-train employees, universities, and other agents.

Young natural scientists were taken as model group. Their training in nanorisk governance has to include social, ethical, communicative and technical aspects associated with NM throughout its lifecycle. It requires that scientists are made familiar with a minimum of hard skills, such as knowledge of the available tool landscape, relevant data and regulations for different NM life cycle stages, beginning with product development and ending with disposal and waste management. Beyond this, broader understanding of principles of 'risk' and 'governance', as well as the role and concerns of different societal stakeholders had to be developed.

The case study was performed according to the project plan based on the stage-gate model (Figure 1). The initially planned second training site UL was exchanged to Venice due to the

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availability of appropriate attendees and the suitable opportunity for integration into the training program of the Nanosafety Training School event 2022 (event program see Figure 5).

Stage-Gate Model WP5.1: CS Training

Figure 1, Stage-Gate Model Case Study Training, intermediate results and key activities of T5.1

In a first step the target groups for training were defined:

- **Master students of the study program “Medical biology”** – the training was designed as one element in the seminar section of the module “Nanomedicine and Nanobiology”,
- **Early career researchers** within nanosafety research – this target group was constituted by the attendees of the **Nanosafety Training School**, 2022 with this year’s subject “Towards Safe & Sustainable by Design Advanced Nanomaterials”.

The next three stages, “Learning targets”, “Training program” and “Knowledge assessment program”, were dependent on available information on “Providing high-quality data and standardized guidance” provided by WP1, “Development of reinforced risk governance tools”, provided by WP2, all integrated in the science-based transdisciplinary risk governance framework including the assigned NANORIGO platform created by WP3. Two different surveys on NRGF assessment were designed, one for evaluation by the training attendees and one by the trainers. In addition, a validation of the NRGF Web-platform was performed and provided to WP3.

The training materials resulting in the course of training program development are made freely available and described in chapter 3.

2. Training program

The entire training program (Figure 2) is structured along the six steps of the NRGF, so trainees are guided through the full process. A focus of the training is on the model case of TiO₂, in close cooperation with case study 6. The program, thus, is anchored in practice, since the trainees learn to apply the NRGF and become familiar with the overall content of the NRGF and its use for solving practical problems.

Figure 2. Conceptual outline of case study “Training”. The NRGF forms the central resource for the planned training activities and, hence, for achieving the teaching objectives. It is contextually linked to additional training resources developed and provided within this case study. In particular, the NRGF is expected to provide resources for the “framing” in phase one and additionally exert a guiding function through the “process” in phase two. In the third phase, students work through their case “TiO₂ in food ban”, particularly in alignment with and relying on the NRGF framework.

For a comprehensive training of most relevant governance aspects on NM a stepwise approach to the centerpiece, the NRGF, was chosen. In a first step (the “framing” phase) the contextual frame is set and boundaries are defined. Explanatory resources concerning basic terms and definitions are provided in order to align the basic understanding and to address differences among individual normative convictions and perception. This step is followed by a second training phase (the “process” phase) with the teaching objective to recognize risk governance as continual process, which can go back and forth, has distinct points of intervention and decision,

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involves or excludes different stakeholders while linking it to basic but also broader questions of NM risk governance principles, tool concepts and publicly available data resources. In a third training phase (the “trial” phase) young scientists, in a collaborative manner, elaborate a case study ‘TiO₂ in food ban’. By identifying and selecting appropriate resources, addressing exemplarily described issues associated with this case and, to some extent, taking different stakeholder’s roles and propositions into account, a joint position paper or presentation is to develop. The training is completed by an assessment of the NRGF, in which students evaluate the usability of NRGF process in regard to nanosafety. Content-related questions reveal understanding of nanorisk governance imparted through NRGF.

Two different training programs were designed and organized. Main differences are the nano-specific prior knowledge required and framing phase, and the different tasks in the “trial” phase.

2.1. Training program with group work, case and paper presentation; Salzburg

Attendees: Master students “Medical Biology” at PLUS

1. Framing & Definition:

The training for nanorisk governance was designed as a last training section in the course of the module Nanomedicine and Nanobiology for master students, containing a lecture part “Nanomaterials – Risk and Medical Applications”, a lab course on Nanomaterials and a seminar on Nanomedical Applications.

2. Risk Governance Process:

A lecture was held about the whole risk governance process using the training material available as video and as slides in Zenodo link ([“The process of risk governance: Walking through the six individual steps for managing the life cycle of risk”](#), files “1_Risk governance_Sabine Hofer.mp4” and “1_Risk governance_Sabine Hofer.pdf”)

3. The ‘TiO₂ CASE’:

The lecture for introduction in the case (Figure 3, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7254145>, “*The TiO₂ case: background and instruction for group work*”) explains the whole story about TiO₂ classification and food ban and includes TiO₂ uptake via different routes (inhalable, ingestion), followed by a group work, in which the students were asked to prepare two presentation, one about the ‘TiO₂ case’ and one about the key publication leading to the decisions made.

No harmonized CLP Classification for TiO₂

Hazard classification	Hazard statement	Nr. of submitters
Not classified		2387
Acute Tox 4 – H332	Harmful if inhaled	63
Acute Tox 4 H312	Harmful in contact with skin	4
Acute Tox 4 H302	Harmful if swallowed	14
Skin Irrit 2 – H315	Causes skin irritation	11
Eye Irrit 2 – H319	Causes serious eye irritation	71
STOT SE 2 – H371	May cause damage to organs	10
Resp Sens 1 – H334	May cause allergy or asthma symptoms or breathing difficulties if inhaled	1
STOT SE 3 – H335	May cause respiratory irritation	76
STOT SE 1 – H372	Cause damage to organs through prolonged or repeated exposure	69
STOT SE 2 – H373	May cause damage to organs through prolonged or repeated exposure	1
Muta 2 – H341	Suspected of causing genetic effects	1
Carc 1B – 350	May cause cancer	9
Carc 2 – H351	Suspected of causing cancer	115
Aqua Chronic 4 – H413	May cause long lasting harmful effects to aquatic life	22

Result of the regulation process

Titanium dioxide: E171 no longer considered safe when used as a food additive

Published: 6 May 2021

EFSA has updated its safety assessment of the food additive titanium dioxide (E 171), following a request by the European Commission in March 2020.

Contents

- FAQ – EFSA 2021 safety assessment of titanium dioxide (E171)
- How to contact us
- Related topic(s)

<https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/news/titanium-dioxide-e171-no-longer-considered-safe-when-used-food-additive>

Figure 3. Example slides from lecture ‘The TiO₂ case’

Two subgroups of six students each were built:

- **Group 1, TiO₂ Inhalation route: French Carcinogenic Classification/Labeling Request, 2016, Inhalation Route, ANSES CLH Report**
- **Group 2, TiO₂ as food additive: EU E171/TiO₂ in Food Ban, 2021, Oral Route, European Commission; Regulation: “TiO₂’s (Food additive E171) genotoxicity cannot be ruled out”, EFSA**

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Both groups had to

- i. prepare and present a synopsis based on delivered ANSES / EFSA reports (<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7254145>, “ANSES CLH report Proposal for Harmonised Classification and Labelling”, “EFSA report: Safety assessment of titanium dioxide (E171) as a food additive”), and
- ii. present the respective key publication (<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7254145>, for group 1 / Inhalation route: “The TiO₂ food ban case: Key publication for TiO₂ - inhalation route”, Danielsen et al., 2020, DOI: [10.1016/j.taap.2019.114830](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.taap.2019.114830); for group 2 / food additive: “The TiO₂ food ban case: Key publication for TiO₂ as food additive”, Bettini et al., 2017, DOI: [10.1038/srep40373](https://doi.org/10.1038/srep40373)).

These (four) presentations were held in the course of the seminar with consecutive discussion.

(a)

Four non-human studies for inhalation route

<p>Thyssen et al., 1978</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Unknown number of female/male mice• Exposure to 0 or 15.95 mg/m³ TiO₂ by inhalation for 6h/day, 5days/week for 12 weeks• Results:<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Not carcinogenic by inhalation• Inflammatory reaction	<p>Lee et al., 1985</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• 400 male and female rats• Exposure to 0, 10, 50, or 250 mg/m³ (6 hr/day, 5 days/week) for 24 months• Results<ul style="list-style-type: none">• ↑ pneumonia, tracheitis with squamous lesions in nasal cavities, high exposure at 250 mg/m³: dust deposition in tracheobronchial lymph nodes, dust accumulations• ↑ bronchioalveolar adenoma in females and males and squamous lesions (mostly keratin cysts) in females at 250 mg/m³
<p>Muhle et al., 1989</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• 344 male and female rats, whole body exposure of 6h/day, 5 days/week for 2 years• Results:<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Not carcinogenic by inhalation• Inflammatory reaction with bronchoalveolar hyperplasia	<p>Heinrich et al., 1995</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Female rats with exposure of 18 h/day, 5 days/week for 2 years with concentration of 7-15 mg/m³ over 8 months, followed by 9 mg/m³ (rats: 16 months; mice: 5 months)• Result:<ul style="list-style-type: none">• ↑ benign keratinizing cystic squamous cell tumours, squamous cell carcinomas, bronchioalveolar adenomas and adenocarcinomas in rats. Not carcinogenic in mice.• Increased mortality, decreased body weight in both species. Impaired clearance function, hyperplasia, interstitial fibrosis in rats

(b)

Re-evaluation of E 171

How it gets to the tissue and what happens?

- Peyer´s patches → disrupted to various organs (mesenteric lymph nodes, liver, spleen, kidney, lungs, heart and reproductive organs)
- Tissue accumulation
- Complicated result interpretation

Figure 2: Peyer's patches in the gut associated lymphoid tissue (GALT)
© researchgate.net

(c)

ECHA classification: Carc 2B – H351 „Suspected of causing cancer“

- increased **pulmonary inflammation** - including **neutrophil influx in bronchoalveolar lavage (BAL) fluid**, after acute, sub-acute and sub-chronic exposure to TiO₂ NMs by either inhalation or intratracheal instillation

Neutrophil influx in BAL fluid:

- correlates with pulmonary acute phase response in terms of **increased serum amyloid A 3 (Saa3) mRNA levels** in lung tissue of mice

Serum amyloid A 3 (Saa3):

- produced in the lungs
- enters systemic circulation as part of high density lipoprotein molecules
- causing reversal of the cholesterol flow → increased formation of foam cells and plaque progression → contribution to the pathogenesis of cardiovascular disease

Visualization & localisation in lung tissue

- 28 days post exposure, histological section, enhanced dark field microscopy
- Tubes
 - alveoli full of micro-agglomerates
- Cubes
 - large aggregates
- BAL fluid cells, 90 days post exposure, TEM
 - Nanoparticle located in vesicles inside macrophage

(d)

Abstract

- Food-grade titanium dioxide (TiO₂) contains a nanoscale particle fraction (TiO₂-NPs)
- Is approved as a white pigment (E 171 in Europe) in common foodstuffs
- Increased risk of chronic intestinal inflammation and carcinogenesis
- Titanium was detected in the immune cells of Peyer's patches (PP) as observed with the TiO₂-NP model NM-105.
- Dendritic cell frequency increased in PP regardless of TiO₂ treatment
- Regulatory T cells involved in dampening inflammatory responses decreased with E 171 → effect still observed after 100 days of treatment
- In all TiO₂-treated rats, stimulation of immune cells isolated from PP showed a decrease in T helper (Th)-1 IFN-γ secretion → splenic Th1/Th17 inflammatory responses sharply increased

Figure 4. Example slides from students' presentations (a) French Carcinogenic Classification/Labeling Request, 2016, ANSES CLH Report, (b) Danielsen et al., <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.taap.2019.114830>, (c) Safety assessment of titanium dioxide (E171), 2021, EFSA, (d) Bettini, S. et al., <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep40373>.

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4. NRGF (Self) Assessment

Subsequently, the whole course was asked to participate in the poll for NRGF assessment.

Questions:

1. How did concerns in regard to TiO₂ come into being? (open answer)
2. Who was initially involved in raising concern towards TiO₂? (select: Authorities/Regulators, Industry, NGOs, Public, Researchers, Risk assessors, Users, Workers)
3. What is to be said about the scientific evidence for TiO₂ hazard (route of exposure, dosing, etc.)? (open answer)
4. What decision was taken in the end for the EU? (select: Safe as food additive, Labelling/warning on food consumer products, Daily uptake recommendation, Food ban)
5. If any societal stakeholder's concerns arise: Should the precautionary principle prevail responsible innovation? (select: yes, always; yes, if the majority thinks so; no, only if there is evidence for a real risk, which cannot be properly managed; no, innovation should always prevail)
6. Pre-assessment: Which risk property would you assign to the "TiO₂ Case"? (select: simple, complex, uncertain, ambiguous)
7. Pre-assessment: Is there an advantage in using a risk governance framework (tools, data, methods) for framing the risk? (select: strong advantage, moderate advantage, no advantage, don't know)
8. Scientific assessment: Do you think, there is sufficient scientific information about TiO₂'s hazards, exposure and vulnerability of affected populations? (strong believe, moderate believe, no, don't know)
9. Scientific assessment: Is there an advantage in using a risk governance framework in synthesizing the knowledge base for subsequent decisions? (select: strong support, moderate support, no support, don't know)
10. Perception, opinion and concern assessment: Do you think that affected stakeholders and the society were sufficiently and early enough involved in the 'TiO₂ case'? (strong believe, moderate believe, no, don't know)
11. Perception, opinion and concern assessment: Is there an advantage in using a risk governance framework for identifying the issues of directly affected stakeholders and

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- the general society? (select: strong advantage, moderate advantage, no advantage, don't know)
12. Risk evaluation: Do you think that in the 'TiO₂ case' accepted criteria by science and society have been applied for reviewing and weighing the synthesized knowledge base for later decision making? (strong believe, moderate believe, no, don't know)
 13. Risk evaluation: Is there an advantage in using a risk governance framework to balance the need for precaution and for enabling responsible innovation? (select: strong advantage, moderate advantage, no advantage, don't know (open answer))
 14. Management: Do you think that in the 'TiO₂ case' the management action 'TiO₂ food ban' was the only option to avoid, retain or transfer the risk? (strong believe, moderate believe, no, don't know)
 15. Management: Is there an advantage in using a risk governance framework to identify available or to design new appropriate risk management options for treatment and regulation of the risk? (select: strong advantage, moderate advantage, no advantage, don't know (open answer) in addition?)
 16. For you as young scientist: What are the most important elements of a risk governance framework (please rank) (user friendly guidance through the framework; data collections; tool collections; communication platform; risk governance process description; e-learning content)
 17. For you as young scientist: Do you think that the regulatory outcome of the 'TiO₂ case' would have been different given that such a risk governance process with all steps would have been applied early? (strong believe, moderate believe, no, don't know)

2.2. Training program with role play on 'TiO₂ food ban', joint position paper; Venice

Attendees: PhD Students and Post-docs, Senior Researchers, Industry Practitioners, Regulators, Policy Makers, Civil Society representatives, anyone else interested in the Safety and Sustainability of Advanced Materials

1. Framing & Definition:

The training on nanorisk governance was designed as the last training section in the course of the Nanosafety Training School 2022, Venice, with this year's subject "Towards Safe & Sustainable by Design Advanced (Nano)materials". The attendees got a preceding five days-

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long and detailed insight in Nanomaterial's "What they are", "Where they go", "What they do", the sustainability lifecycle and selected steps in risk governance including tooling and modeling (Figure 5).

The full program is available at https://bit.ly/nanovenice22_program_with_presentations.

 Università
Ca' Foscari
Venezia

Dates: May 15–20 2022, Venue: Venice, [Auditorium Santa Margherita](#) of Università Ca' Foscari Venezia

Nanosafety Training School: Towards Safe & Sustainable by Design Advanced (Nano)materials

	Sunday, 15 th May	Monday, 16 th May	Tuesday, 17 th May	Wednesday, 18 th May	Thursday, 19 th May	Friday, 20 th May
08:30–09:00		Arrival	Arrival	Arrival	Arrival	Arrival
09:00–10:30		What they are: physical-chemical identity - Intrinsic properties (Andrea Brunelli, Elena Badetti Miguel Bañares)	Where they go: human bio-distribution and exposure (Lang Tran)	Grouping (Andrea Haase V, Mario Pink, HARMLESS project Vicki Stone)	Introduction to sustainability life cycle assessment (SLCA) and Environmental sustainability assessment: Hands-on session on LCA (Lisa Pizzo/Alex Zabeo)	Risk Governance Interactive session: Role-play (Martin Himly, Susanne Resch Norbert Hofstaetter Phil Sayre Damjana Drobné V Sabine Hofer Jose Vicente Tarazona)
10:30–11:00		Coffee break	Coffee break	Coffee break	Coffee break	Coffee break
11:00–12:30		What they are: physical-chemical identity – Extrinsic "system dependent" properties (Anna Costa Iseult Lynch V)	What they do: human toxicity & human health (Otmar Schmid Sabine Hofer / Norbert Hofstaetter)	Risk Assessment and Management (Neil Hunt)	Hands-on session on Social LCA / LCC analysis (Sonia Martel Martin, Jesús Ibañez)	Risk Governance Interactive session: Role-play (see above)
12:30–14:00		Lunch	Lunch	Lunch	Lunch	Closing remarks
14:00–15:00	Registration	Where they go: lifecycle release (Bernd Nowack Camilla Delpivo, SAbYNA project)	What they do: environmental toxicity (Teresa F. Fernandes V)	Data FAIRness V (Martine Bakker Iseult Lynch)	13:30–14:00 NSC ECRs initiative presentation (Ilaria Zanoni Stefania Melandri David Burrucco Subirà) 14:00–15:00 Ways to promote your research	V = virtually attending, virtual talk
15:00–15:30		15:30–15:45 Coffee break	Coffee break	Coffee break	Coffee break	
15:30–17:00	15:30 Welcome (Antonio Marcomini Danail Hristozov Stefania Melandri) 15:45 NanoSafety Cluster perspective (Eva Valsami-Jones V) 16:15 Safe and sustainable by design chemicals and materials – framework for the definition of SSbD criteria (Juan Riego Sintas)	15:45–17:15 Where they go: environmental fate and exposure V (Haralambos Sarimveis, Periklis Tsiros, Pantelis Karatzas, Philip Doganis – NanoCommons & NanoSolveIT projects)	15:30–17:30 Results for hands-on sessions: modeling (Georgia Tsiliki Vladimir Lobaskin, Ian Rouse Benjami Martorell Masip)	Hands-on session on data quality assessment (Camilla Delpivo, SAbYNA project Gianpietro Basei Martin Himly)	Frameworks and tools for Safe by Design of nanomaterials (Andrea Porcari Beatrice Salieri Alexander C. Ø. Jensen Neeraj Shandilya Gustavo Gonzalez, Gov4Nano project)	
17:00–18:30	17:00 Industrial Perspective (Wibke Lötsberg V) 17:45 Q&A session	17:15–18:30 Closing: Historical perspective of Nano Safety (Georgios Katalagariannakis)	17:30–19:30 Guided walking tour in Venice	DSS on risk assessment and management (Alex Zabeo Alexander Christian Østerskov Jensen)	A Different View: U.S. Regulatory Assessments for the use of Carbon Nanotubes in Batteries (Phil Sayre) 17:30–19:30 Free time 19:30 Social dinner	
	18:30 Welcome cocktail					

Figure 5. Agenda – 2022 Training School Venice; NRGF training marked in red.

2. Risk Governance Process:

A lecture was held covering the entire risk governance process using the training material available as video and as slides (["The process of risk governance: Walking through the six individual steps for managing the life cycle of risk"](#), files "[1_Risk governance_Sabine Hofer.mp4](#)" and "[1_Risk governance_Sabine Hofer.pdf](#)")

3. The CASE 'TiO₂ in food ban':

Consecutive to the virtual lecture for introduction in the case (<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7254145>, "[The TiO₂ case a perspective on the history and how it developed](#)", Figure 6), the summarized results of the most relevant different studies concerning TiO₂ as food additive were presented (<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7254145>, "[TiO₂ as food additive – documents in a nutshell](#)").

Steps in TiO₂ classification

Figure 6. Example slide from lecture 'The TiO₂ case'

For the following role play the attendees were split into 4 stakeholder groups **scientists**, **public**, **regulators** and **industry**, to discuss – assisted by four experts - the case with the final aim to prepare for the subsequent panel discussion with one representative from each group. In addition, the panel had then to create a 120 -150 words statement, consensually agreed by all four stakeholder groups, containing background, strength of the evidence, definition of concern and recommendation for EC decision (<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7254145>, "The TiO₂ case: background and instruction for role play").

The following statement of the "Nanorisk Governance" panel was created in Venice: "Concerning the ban of Titanium dioxide dated February 2022, the panel concluded that there is lack of communication between all stakeholders. As a result, no common conclusion was reached on the case study. The panel therefore suggests that equal discussion among regulators, scientists, industries, and society is needed. Ideally, discussion must be initiated at the early stages of product development, during the design phase. To involve society into the decision-making process, the panel suggest that NGOs, worker unions etc. should have a place in the discussion. We urge the EC to help facilitate the communication between all stakeholders by creating a level playing field platform".

4. NRGF (Self) Assessment

Subsequently, all attendees were asked to participate in the poll for NRGF assessment, identical to the poll, carried out in Salzburg.

3. Available training materials

Different types of educational materials, such as videos (V), posters (P), documents (D), presentation slides (S) indicated in column 1, that were established at respective outreach and training events for the primary target groups are overviewed in the Table 1 below. The table also includes the training material used in the two training programs presented in chapter 2. As target groups **early career researchers** (ECR) and **experts and trainers** (EXP) were selected. Their content and potential application in trainings is described in the following chapters.

Table 1. Training material

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What	For Whom ECR EXP	Where
Primary target group: early career researchers		
<p>S From basic science to risk governance</p> <p>V</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Linking nanosafety data and knowledge readiness with the social dimension of risk governance - The process of risk governance: Walking through the six individual steps for managing the life cycle of risk - Quality assurance of data, defined by the Knowledge Readiness Level (KaRL) - The risk governance process to warrant inclusiveness for different values into the risk/benefit estimation - Discussion on risk governance - What would we miss without risk governance <p>D The TiO₂ food ban case: Key publication for TiO₂ as food additive</p> <p>D The TiO₂ food ban case: Key publication for TiO₂ - inhalation route</p> <p>D TiO₂ as food additive – documents in a nutshell</p> <p>D EFSA report: Safety assessment of titanium dioxide (E171) as a food additive</p> <p>D ANSES CLH report Proposal for Harmonised Classification and Labelling</p> <p>V Exposure to inhalable nanomaterial & dose equivalence: Integration of hazard identification and risk assessment</p>	<p>✓</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/record/5057543#.YbohplxmUk</p> <p>https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=T_u-OnGRTEw</p> <p>DOI: 10.1038/srep40373</p> <p>DOI: 10.1016/j.taap.2019.114830</p> <p>http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7254145</p> <p>http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7254145</p> <p>http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7254145</p> <p>https://youtu.be/qCOPNrs3t38</p>
Primary target group: experts and trainers		
<p>S Features of nanoRGFs in development & current NRG concepts (NSC Education Day):</p> <p>V</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What do we need a NRG Council for, who are its stakeholders and what are their needs? - Insight into the nanorisk governance process guided by the NANORIGO NRG framework - Requirements on NRG frameworks by insurances and other societal stakeholders <p>S The purpose of a risk governance framework (objects, aims, stakeholders, steps, risk management escalator)</p>	<p>✓</p> <p>✓</p> <p>✓</p> <p>✓</p>	<p>https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4314975</p> <p>https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5Q5KcvlFZGI</p> <p>Appendix 1</p>

D5.2 Report: Case study on training

S Making sense of the “rubber granulate” case with the NRGF: A case study for using the framework Posters at the EuroNanoForum 2021	✓	✓	Appendix 2
P - Data Management for Nanotechnology Risk Governance		✓	https://NANORIGO.eu/results/publications/
		✓	https://NANORIGO.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/NMBP-13-NRG-Data-Group-poster-ENF2021.pdf
P - NRGF - adaption of the IRGC approach		✓	https://NANORIGO.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/NMBP-13-NRGF-poster-ENF2021.pdf
P - A new Council for the Governance of Nanotechnology-related Risk		✓	https://NANORIGO.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/NMBP-13-NRGC-poster2-ENF2021.pdf
P - Risk Governance of Nanomaterials (NMBP-13 Cluster Three European Projects Working Together)		✓	https://NANORIGO.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/NMBP-13-poster-ENF2021.pdf
P - The NANORIGO Project		✓	https://NANORIGO.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/NANORIGO-poster-ENF2021.pdf
D Illustrating and applying the NANORIGO framework with Smart Nanomaterials	✓	✓	Appendix 3
S Role play: Applying the NANORIGO framework with Smart Nanomaterials	✓	✓	Appendix 4
S The TiO₂ case: a perspective on the history and how it developed	✓	✓	http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7254145
S The TiO₂ case: background and instruction for group work		✓	http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7254145
S The TiO₂ case: background and instruction for role play		✓	http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7254145

3.1. Training material for primary target group “early career researchers”

From basic science to risk governance - “Risk assessment with social dimension: how does risk governance differ from risk assessment or management?”

The training material was designed for the session “Risk Governance” at the 10th Nanosafety Training School: From Basic Science to Risk Governance, 2021. The session, carried out by Martin Himly (PLUS), Sabine Hofer (PLUS), Norbert Hofstätter (PLUS), Dmitri Ciornii (BAM) and Daan Schuurbiens (DPF), is available as videos and as slide shows (<https://zenodo.org/record/5057543#.YbohplkxmUk>, https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=T_u-OnGRTEw) and contains the following topics:

- Linking nanosafety data and knowledge readiness with the social dimension of risk governance
- Introduction in the process of (nano)risk governance and the NANORIGO process steps
- Quality assurance of data, defined by the Knowledge Readiness Level (KaRL), which, in analogy to NASA’s Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs), defines a categorization system of data, information, and knowledge which enables transformation of data and information into functional knowledge for nanorisk governance
- Different stakeholder views and how socioeconomic aspects can be incorporated into the risk governance process to warrant inclusiveness for different values into the risk/benefit estimation
- Discussion on risk governance
- What would we miss without risk governance

Figure 7. Snap shots from the session on “Risk assessment with social dimension”.

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Key documents for 'TiO₂ case' (group work and role play)

The documents were collected and prepared as basic material for the training programs (see chapter 2, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7254145>).

- Key publication for TiO₂ as food additive (Bettini, S. *et al.*; 2017; <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep40373>)
- Key publication for TiO₂ - inhalation route (Danielsen *et al.*; 2020; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.taap.2019.114830>)
- TiO₂ as food additive – documents in a nutshell: summary of the most important statements
- EFSA report: Safety assessment of TiO₂ (E171) as a food additive (scientific opinion)
- ANSES CLH report Proposal for Harmonised Classification and Labelling

Exposure to inhalable nanomaterial & dose equivalence: Integration of hazard identification and risk assessment (Sabine Hofer)

In the course of the EuroNanoForum 2021 (Figure 8) Sabine Hofer (PLUS) talked about the exposure to inhalable nanomaterial and in this context about the need of coherent integration of hazard identification, such as exposure to nanomaterial, with tools of risk assessment. Nanoparticle dosimetry data for both worlds – *in vivo* and *in vitro* - have to be conclusively linked. The video is available on the NSC-YouTube-Channel (<https://youtu.be/qCOPNrs3t38>).

Dose equivalence library: What's for?

Guidance for RA / LCA tools and data quality assessment

FAIR: findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable
NRGF: Nano risk governance framework

This project has received funding from The European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant agreement 814530.

Figure 8. Example slide discussing the integration of hazard identification and risk assessment by applying a dose equivalence library.

3.2. Training material for primary target group “experts and trainers”

Features of nanoRGFs in development & current NRCG concepts:

In the course of the NSC Education Day @ NanoSafe Digital Congress 2020, block “NanoRisk Governance & Safe-by-Design concepts - fit for translation to sustainable development?”, slides and videos were made available (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4314975>, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5Q5KcvIFZGI>), which can be used as training material:

- What do we need an NRG Council for, who are its stakeholders and what are their needs? (Marie-Valentine Florin, EPFL)

Figure 9. Example slide introducing the concept of a risk governance council.

- Insight into the nanorisk governance process guided by the NANORIGO NRG framework (Arto Säämänen, FIOH)

Risk Governance Framework

<https://irgc.org/risk-governance/irgc-risk-governance-framework/>

NANORIGO adaptation to nanotechnology

Figure 10. Example slide discussing the functionality of the risk governance framework.

D5.2 Report: Case study on training

- Requirements on NRGF by insurances and societal stakeholders (Martin Mullins, TGO)

The purpose of a risk governance framework (objects, aims, stakeholders, steps, risk management escalator) (Arto Säämänen, FIOH):

The slide show (Appendix 1) was used at ACHEMA Pulse, 2021 and concerns the purpose of a risk governance framework by using the showcase on rubber tyres and can be used as basis for respective training sessions.

What is the issue?

Figure 11. Example slide discussing the nanosafety issues of rubber tyres wear.

- Making sense of the “rubber granulate” case with the NRGF: A case study for using the framework (Marie-Valentine Florin, EPFL)

The slides (Appendix 2) explain the whole risk governance process reflecting each NRGF step by using the “rubber granulate” case.

2016 : public opinion concerns in the NL (1)

- Health concerns
>> new scientific technical assesment

Figure 12. Example slide discussing NRG using the “rubber granulate” case.

Posters at the EuroNanoForum 2021

Five posters (Figure 13; <https://nanorigo.eu/results/publications>), explaining Data Management for Nanotechnology Risk Governance, the adaption of the IRGC approach, the purpose of a risk governance council, the collaboration of the three NMBP-13 projects in nanorisk governance and the NANORIGO project as a whole can be integrated in training sessions, when discussing the aims of nanorisk governance.

Data Management for Nanotechnology Risk Governance

Martine Bakker, Damjana Drobne, Nina Jeliazkova, Antreas Afantitis, Egon Willighagen and Iseult Lynch

Data management core group: overall role and remit

The three NMBP-13 projects have a common data management core group with delegates from each of the three projects. Joint milestones were defined for the areas depicted below:

Data management plans

- covering all aspects & all types of data
- how we manage them effectively & efficiently
- alignment across 3 projects.

Quality/fitness for re-use scoring of datasets

- consensus & development of standards
- implementation of tools & workflows

Datasets to support case studies

- integrated datasets will be compiled using agreed standards

Interoperability and automation

- through optimisation of uptake of existing tools and development of "bridging" tools

Whereas NANORIGO is focused on defining concepts and user needs, in RiskGone and Gov4nano the emphasis is on operationalisation / implementation of nanosafety data and FAIR solutions. Together, the 3 projects cover the whole data management spectrum to enable the risk governance of nanomaterials and provide knowledge in a useful format for the Nanomaterials Risk Governance Council (NRGC) once established.

Conceptualisation & user needs documentation

Community consensus on data standards (metadata, FAIR metrics) => stepwise SOP for data quality / re-usability

Operationalisation & automation (tooling) to facilitate data re-use, decision making & sustainability

Joint Milestone: Glossary of key terms related to data management

TERM	DEFINITION	PROJECT
Dataset	A digital representation of a collection of related data that can be used to analyse and interpret information.	Gov4Nano
Database	A structured set of data held together in a computer system.	RiskGone
DBMS	Software that interacts with the users, applications and the database itself to capture and analyze data.	NANORIGO
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable	All projects
Metadata	Data about data, which describes an object and its relationships.	All projects
API	Application Programming Interface	All projects
Tool	Software that helps in performing a specific task.	All projects

"Living document" to support needs of all Core groups & projects

Joint Milestone: Prioritization of databases to make interoperable

- Inventory of databases – content / maintenance / API access
- Inventory of data uses (by NRGC)
- Analysis and synthesis of priority list in progress

Alignment with NRGC needs & Cloud Platform architecture

Joint Milestone: Agreed access and criteria for curating and verifying / validating older project datasets for re-usability

Paper in preparation on:

- Optimization and automation of workflows
 - for evaluation of dataset quality, completeness and fitness of purpose
 - for re-use by diverse end-users and stakeholders

Work in progress

Contributors from NANORIGO, Gov4nano, RiskGone, NanoCommons, NanoSolveIT and NanoInformaTIX projects.

Automation of workflows

Automatic quality scoring

Data curation

Reliability of study design

FAIR data

Meta-data

Data translation for tools

Re-usability

Meta-analysis of data

Joint milestones on alignment of the project's data management plans

Work in progress

Joint Plan for jointly created outputs & NRGC inputs

NMBP-13 Collaboration: 3 projects; 82 partners; 17 EU countries and Brazil, India, Iran, Switzerland, South Africa, Republic of Korea, the UK, and the USA; **Budget:** € 18.3 million; **Duration:** January 2019 – February 2023

www.gov4nano.eu
 www.nanorigo.eu
 www.riskgone.eu

These projects have received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 814425, 814401 and 814530.

Nanotechnology Risk Governance Framework (NRGF) – adaptation of the IRGC approach

Arto Säämänen^a, Marie-Valentine Florin^b, Francisco Huertas^c, Arantxa Ballesteros^c, Piet Sellke^d, Anna-Kaisa Viitanen^a, Panagiotis Isigonis^e, Nils Bohmer^f, Dalila Antunes^g, Keld Alstrup Jensen^h

It has been widely acknowledged that the **risk governance of nanotechnology** should be based on a clear understanding of risk, its management practices, and the societal risk perception by all stakeholders. The Risk Governance Framework of the International Risk Governance Center (IRGC) describes processes aiming to provide and structure scientific evidence about a risk in a societal context.

The **NANORIGO, RiskGONE and GOV4NANO** projects consider this framework along with the ISO 21505 and ISO 31000 standards modified in caLIBRAte to fit nanotechnology, its products and contiguous frameworks. The NRGF provides guidance for early identification, assessment, management and communication of risks, involving multiple stakeholders, considering the social impacts of the various uses of nanoproducts, and coupling risk benefit assessment.

It integrates selected **methods, tools and best practices** that can improve or complement existing practices for safety and risk management. **Stakeholder needs**, as continuously identified, are incorporated in the NRGF to enable tailored development for multiple stakeholder groups. The NRGF comprises of interlinked steps and cross-cutting core functions and serves as the integrator of important concepts and principles, tools and illustrations. The framework is converted to **web-based solutions** also including the use of FAIR data to facilitate its' interactive and flexible use.

Governance	Involvement
Refers to the actions, processes, traditions and institutions by which authority is exercised and decisions are taken and implemented.	Involves multi-disciplinary sciences and multi-stakeholder approaches.
Framework	
For risk governance this is based on a defined and structured process to addressing risk in a comprehensive and holistic manner.	
A future-proof, operational Nano Risk Governance Framework	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Based on the IRGC Framework Integrates scientific data and operational tools into a relevant and reliable and transparent decision framework, trusted among stakeholders Aimed at a participative and pro-active form of governance Based on existing infrastructure & across all relevant domains a.o. chemicals, biocides, consumer products, food, medicine Connecting key organizations and stakeholders (EU and global) 	

JM9 Shared working documents on Nano Risk Governance Framework & Portal

JM9 Identification of agreed and shared needs for NRGF, based on stakeholder activities and options of the Framework prototype

JM10 Verification that the requirements for the NRGF are covered by the content of the cloud/portal-platform/Web tool(s) from all three projects

JM17 Final version of the Risk Governance Framework

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NMBP-13 Collaboration: 3 projects; 82 partners; 17 EU countries and Brazil, India, Iran, Switzerland, South Africa, Republic of Korea, the UK, and the USA; **Budget:** € 18.3 million; **Duration:** January 2019 – February 2023

www.gov4nano.eu
 www.nanorigo.eu
 www.riskgone.eu

These projects have received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 814425, 814401 and 814530

A New Council for the Governance of Nanotechnology-related Risk

Marie-Valentine Florin^a, Rob Aitken^b, Panagiotis Isgonis^c, Monique Groenewold^d,
Janeck Scott-Fordsmand^e, Tommaso Serchi^f, Dalila Antunes^g, Arto Säämänen^h, Andrea Porcariⁱ

The EC Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability, the Green Deal, and other initiatives in Europe, indicate an ambition regarding safety, sustainability, and circularity of chemicals, towards a non-toxic environment. Innovation brings potential for economic growth and addressing societal and environmental challenges. However, innovation often comes with high uncertainty regarding its risks. Concerns are raised on the access of all important actors to high-quality data, technical risk assessment, public perception and acceptance, and regulatory harmonisation and effectiveness, among other aspects. Improvements are needed in how risks to human health and the environment are assessed, managed and communicated.

To address these challenges, three H2020 projects of the NMBP-13 call (NANORIGO, RiskGONE and Gov4Nano) are working to improve the governance of nanorisks in Europe. They are jointly developing the concept of a new organisation tasked with collecting, sharing and disseminating insight for governing risks from nano-based products. The Nanotechnology Risk Governance Council (NRGC) will be an independent organisation with the goal to improve the governance of benefits and risks, now and for the long-term.

Mission and Goals of the NRGC

Activities of the NRGC

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These projects have received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 814425, 814401 and 814530

Risk Governance of Nanomaterials

The Challenge:

Nanotechnology impacts a broad range of industries and applications. Yet, the interaction of engineered nanomaterials with the living environment is complex and is marked by uncertainty and ambiguity. As a result, there is an urgent need to develop appropriate governance structures, to ensure the trust of all stakeholders.

NMBP-13 Cluster Three European Projects Working Together

The Approach:

Three large independent European projects are collaborating in this endeavour. The partners involved have a long history of research to understand the impacts of nanomaterials on human health and the environment, and have participated in all major European and National projects dealing with these topics.

Although each of the projects has its own unique approach and objectives, they share common goals and visions which will be strengthened by constructive cooperation involving all stakeholders across Europe.

Expected Outcomes

A Nanotechnology Risk Governance Portal (NRGP)

An NRGF that is built on sound scientific data and informatics tools. The data and tools, SOPs, and guidelines that are generated will be validated, standardized, as well as progressive, and will be made accessible to all stakeholders. The creation of the portal aligns with the workplans of the three projects.

A Nanotechnology Risk Governance Framework (NRGF)

An operational, trans-disciplinary NRGF that integrates exposure, hazard and risk assessment tools with those assessing ethical, legal, social, and environmental aspects, and further supports responsible research and innovation (RRI).

A Nanotechnology Risk Governance Council (NRGC)

A sustainable NRGC that implements the NRGF and engages with all stakeholders in a proactive, participative, and transparent manner. The NRGC will be a 'trusted environment' to address new issues as they may arise. The NRGC goals of knowledge sharing and access to information will be supported by the NRGF.

The Development Timelines and Processes

Fig.1 The NRGF development process

Fig.2 The NRGC and NRGF development process

We want to hear your views: Join the Stakeholder Community: www.tinyurl.com/NMBP13Stakeholder.

NMBP-13 Collaboration: 3 projects; 82 partners; 17 EU countries and Brazil, India, Iran, Switzerland, South Africa, Republic of Korea, the UK, and the USA; **Budget:** € 18.3 million; **Duration:** January 2019 – February 2023

www.gov4nano.eu www.nanorigo.eu www.riskgone.eu

These projects have received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 814425, 814401 and 814530

NANORIGO

A Risk Governance Framework and Council for Nanomaterials and Nano-enabled Products

ABOUT NANORIGO

NANORIGO (**NANO**technology **Risk GO**vernance) started on 1st January 2019. Coordinated by Aarhus University and involving 28 other partners from across Europe, this 50-month, €4.7 million project is developing and implementing a transparent, transdisciplinary and active Risk Governance Framework (RGF) for manufactured nanomaterials and nano-enabled products.

The RGF will be developed through engagement with stakeholders across research, industry, regulation and civil society, and will be based on high-quality scientific data and tools for the physicochemical (pc) characterization of nanomaterials, and the assessment of exposure, hazard and risk for humans and the environment.

THE NANORIGO APPROACH

Risk management strategies based on reinforced tools for guidance and decision-making developed for risk assessment

The RGF uses a life-cycle perspective and integrates available knowledge on ethical, social, environmental, and economic concerns into a user-friendly format.

Validated methodologies to identify potential hazard and exposure

This format can be easily adapted and transferred into regulation for hazard, exposure and risk assessment and management of nanomaterials.

Web-based information and communication platform to facilitate access to good quality data and a clear risk understanding of stakeholders, and their valuable feedback

EXPECTED RESULTS

- A transparent, self-sustained and science-based European Nanotechnology Risk Governance Council (NRGC)
- Transparent Nanotechnology Risk Governance Framework (NRGF) tools for managing possible nanotechnologies risks
- Availability of high-quality data for decision making
- Consistency of approaches in all EU Member States and internationally

THE IMPACT

For the first time, all stakeholders will be brought together under a common “umbrella” to share and integrate the most appropriate governance tools, frameworks and plans for future scientific and regulatory research and to foster consistency of management approaches in the EU and synergies internationally.

3 PROJECTS – 1 MISSION

Three large independent European projects are collaborating in this endeavour:

MORE INFORMATION:

Project Coordinator: Aarhus University, Janeck James Scott-Fordsmand (jsf@bios.au.dk)

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NANORIGO has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under the grant agreement No. 814530

Figure 13. Posters on display at the ENF 2021 for discussion about nanorisk governance

D5.2 Report: Case study on training

Applying NANORIGO framework for Smart Nanomaterials (Marie-Valentine Florin, EPFL)

The provided slides (Appendix 4) can be used for a role play on applying nanorisk governance for smart nanomaterials (SNM) to discuss SNM-related challenges and opportunities from three different stakeholders' viewpoints: regulators, industry and NGOs (Figure 14). Appendix 3 and 4 present the main outcome of this role play and other analysis with regards to (a) applying the framework to the case of SNM and (b) stakeholders' views.

Group 1: regulators

Facilitators: Martin Mullins, Marie-Valentine Florin

Goal of regulators is to ensure safety and sustainability of nanomaterials, before they are placed on the market, without constraining innovation.

- Assessment of risks from SNM
 - What do you know and don't know?
 - What do you need to know, how?
- Management of risks from SNM
 - Are the tools, existing procedures applicable?
 - Suggestions for regulation
- Communication
 - What would you say about risks and benefits from smart nanomaterials?
- About the NRGCC:
 - How would the presence/availability of RGC impact on regulatory processes
 - Would you use the RGC as resource?

Group 2: industry

Facilitators: Mark Morrison, Nils Bohmer

Goal of industry is to develop and produce nanomaterials, and place them on the market. Safety and sustainability matter but innovation drives economic competitiveness.

- Assessment of risks from SNM
 - What do you know and don't know?
 - What do you need to know, how?
- Management of risks from SNM
 - Are the tools, existing procedures applicable?
 - Suggestions for regulation
- Communication
 - What would you say about risks and benefits from smart nanomaterials?

Group 3: NGOs / CSOs

Facilitators: Christina Benighaus, Daan Schuurbiens

Goal of NGOs/CSOs is to act to represent the interest of the general public, and exercise their power through expertise, awareness raising, advocacy activities and public activism, for instance to influence policy contents and its adequate implementation

- Assessment of risks from SNM:
 - What do you know and don't know?
 - What do you need to know, how?
- Management of risks from SNM:
 - Are the tools, existing procedures applicable?
 - Suggestions for regulation
- Communication
 - What would you say about risks and benefits from smart nanomaterials?

Figure 14. Guidelines and issues for the three different stakeholder's groups (regulators, industry and NGOs) in the role play "SNM-related challenges and opportunities".

Background and training instructions for 'TiO₂ case' (group work and role play)

The three slide shows ("The TiO₂ case: a perspective on the history and how it developed", "The TiO₂ case: background and instruction for group work", "The TiO₂ case: background and instruction for role play"; <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7254145>) are intended to be used in the two training programs as attunement and background information of the TiO₂ case and as work instruction for the students.

Figure 15. Example slide discussing the TiO₂ food ban decision process.

4. Survey on NRGF – trainers

In addition to the designers of both training events, experts in the field of nanorisk governance and in their role as trainers were asked to participate in a survey as part of the NRGF (self)assessment. 25 persons completed the poll containing NRGF related questions, classified in eight sections, a section for general questions, six sections for each NRGF step, and a section concerning the individual experiences (Trainer survey form, Appendix 5). Each section was introduced by explanatory text about the training goal at this point.

4.1. Survey questions

Section A: General questions

The multi-dimensionality of risk, the complexity and variety of strategic options to deal with risk, and the mandatory scientific and social discourse cannot be covered by the means of traditional risk assessment and management.

Thus, a transparent, transdisciplinary and comprehensive Risk Governance Framework (NRGF) for manufactured nanomaterials (NM) and nano-enabled products (NEP), based on the use of scientific high-quality data and tools, communication and engagement with all stakeholders, and embedded in European regulation and legislation was developed.

Organizations that will use the RGF will do it for the purpose of aligning, integrating and transferring the most advanced science-based tools and knowledge on NM physicochemical characterization, exposure and hazard into regulatory human and environmental risk and safety assessment and management.

D5.2 Report: Case study on training

A1. Training in the context of nanosafety research: From your point of view, what are the most important teaching goals in regard to a risk governance training for young scientists?

open question

A2. Training in the context of nanosafety research: From your point of view, what are the most important elements of a risk governance framework?

- *Easy to access internet landing page*
- *User friendly guidance through the framework*
- *Data collections; Tool collections*
- *Communication platform*
- *Risk governance process description*
- *E-learning content*
- *Risk governance council*
- *Experts' network*

Section B: Pre-assessment phase: Define the issue, frame boundaries, identify existing conventions

Learning targets and teaching content:

The purpose of the pre-assessment is to frame the risk, to place an early warning, and to prepare for handling the risk. Pre-assessment involves relevant actors and identifies potential stakeholder groups for subsequent inclusion. It has to capture the various perspectives on the potential risk (simple, complex, uncertain, ambiguous), but also its opportunities, and strategies for addressing it.

Pre-assessment is setting the stage in the governance process. Erroneous decisions at this point of framing are the most critical, because here the agenda for the subsequent steps is defined.

B1. How essential are these teaching goals for a comprehensive understanding of risk governance?

- *very essential*
- *essential*
- *not essential*
- *don't know*

B2. What is your most important teaching goal at this point?

open question

D5.2 Report: Case study on training

B3. Pre-assessment: How well is the NRGF process / NANORIGO Portal aligned with your teaching goal?

- *very well aligned*
- *aligned*
- *not aligned*
- *don't know*

B4. Pre-assessment: How supportive is the NRGF process / NANORIGO portal to prepare for your training session?

Efficiency (less time consuming, more cost effective)

- *very supportive*
- *supportive*
- *not supportive*
- *don't know*

Effectivity (complete, consistent, state of the art training)

- *very supportive*
- *supportive*
- *not supportive*
- *don't know*

Section C: Technical, scientific assessment phase: Hazard, exposure & & vulnerability; consequence assessment

Teaching goals and content:

The purpose of this step is to perform an analytical and technical assessment and to collect existing information about NMs' hazards, exposure and vulnerability of affected populations. Probability of occurrence and extent of harm and severity of consequences must be assessed, through appropriate models for human and environmental risk assessment.

Risk assessment synthesizes the knowledge base for subsequent decisions, including what options are available for preventing, mitigating, adapting to or approving the risk. Information for risk assessment studies is provided by particular safety studies and agreed upon methods, but due to the complex nature of NMs, these may be finally insufficient for an unambiguous risk assessment outcome.

C1. How essential are these teaching goals for a comprehensive understanding of risk governance?

D5.2 Report: Case study on training

- *very essential*
- *essential*
- *not essential*
- *don't know*

C2. What is your most important teaching goal at this point?

open question

C3. Technical, scientific assessment: How well is the NRGF process / NANORIGO Portal aligned with your teaching goal?

- *very well aligned*
- *aligned*
- *not aligned*
- *don't know*

C4. Technical, scientific assessment: How supportive is the NRGF process / NANORIGO portal to prepare for your training session?

Efficiency (less time consuming, more cost effective)

- *very supportive*
- *supportive*
- *not supportive*
- *don't know*

Effectivity (complete, consistent, state of the art training)

- *very supportive*
- *supportive*
- *not supportive*
- *don't know*

Section D: Opinion & concern assessment phase: Capture the opinions, perceptions & concerns of affected populations

Teaching goals and content:

Concern assessment has to identify the opinions, perceptions, and concerns of directly affected stakeholders but also the socio-economic impact and economic benefits or harm of indirectly affected populations. Uncertainty in the context of new technologies raises the bar for the acceptance of nanotechnology-based products, because human behavior and decision making are driven by bounded rationality.

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This makes clear that inclusiveness – “being heard” and informed participation of relevant stakeholders is the key in this stage. Information is the key to align perception driven decisions with decisions based on the outcomes of a technical risk assessment.

D1. How essential are these teaching goals for a comprehensive understanding of risk governance?

- *very essential*
- *essential*
- *not essential*
- *don't know*

D2. What is your most important teaching goal at this point?

open question

D3. Opinion & Concern Assessment: How well is the NRGF process / NANORIGO Portal aligned with your teaching goal?

- *very well aligned*
- *aligned*
- *not aligned*
- *don't know*

D4. Opinion & Concern Assessment: How supportive is the NRGF process / NANORIGO portal to prepare for your training session?

Efficiency (less time consuming, more cost effective)

- *very supportive*
- *supportive*
- *not supportive*
- *don't know*

Effectivity (complete, consistent, state of the art training)

- *very supportive*
- *supportive*
- *not supportive*
- *don't know*

Section E: Evaluation phase: Characterization of the risk

Teaching goals and content:

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Risk evaluation is a phase of reflectiveness and accountable judgement, reviewing and weighing the outcome of pre-assessment, technical risk and concern assessment with criteria accepted by science and society.

It collects and summarizes information of all 3 preceding steps and reflects it from a decision-making perspective.

The final target is to prepare a foundation and to propose a strategy for the risk management phase, which can be led either by the principles of precautionary, or being dominated by the strategy of risk acceptability, risk sharing and mitigation, hence enabling responsible innovation.

However, acceptance is frequently a matter of trade-offs between risks and benefits on a qualitative scale.

E1. How essential are these teaching goals for a comprehensive understanding of risk governance?

- *very essential*
- *essential*
- *not essential*
- *don't know*

E2. What is your most important teaching goal at this point?

open question

E3. Evaluation: How well is the NRGF process / NANORIGO Portal aligned with your teaching goal?

- *very well aligned*
- *aligned*
- *not aligned*
- *don't know*

E4. Evaluation: How supportive is the NRGF process / NANORIGO portal to prepare for your training session?

Efficiency (less time consuming, more cost effective)

- *very supportive*
- *supportive*
- *not supportive*
- *don't know*

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Effectivity (complete, consistent, state of the art training)

- *very supportive*
- *supportive*
- *not supportive*
- *don't know*

Section F: Management phase: Treatment and regulation of the risk

Teaching goals and content:

Risk management is a process that addresses the treatment and regulation of a risk by development and implementation of the actions and remedies required to avoid, retain, reduce or transfer the risk.

For standard risks, standard management instruments are frequently available and have to be appropriately evaluated, selected and adopted. However, sometimes an accepted and harmonized approach is not available, thus the design and generation of new risk management options may be needed.

An implemented risk management strategy has to cover the whole risk life-cycle, thus is made-to-last.

F1. How essential are these teaching goals for a comprehensive understanding of risk governance?

- *very essential*
- *essential*
- *not essential*
- *don't know*

F2. What is your most important teaching goal at this point?

open question

F3. Management: How well is the NRGF process / NANORIGO Portal aligned with your teaching goal?

- *very well aligned*
- *aligned*
- *not aligned*
- *don't know*

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F4. Management: How supportive is the NRGF process / NANORIGO portal to prepare for your training session?

Efficiency (less time consuming, more cost effective)

- *very supportive*
- *supportive*
- *not supportive*
- *don't know*

Effectivity (complete, consistent, state of the art training)

- *very supportive*
- *supportive*
- *not supportive*
- *don't know*

Section G: Monitoring & feedback phase: Monitoring the performance, evaluating and providing feedback

Teaching goals and content:

Monitoring of risk, monitoring the implemented risk management strategy and measures is critical, in particular to keep up with an evolving technical and regulatory environment, changes in the societal perception and tolerance to risk or increasing uncertainty or ambiguity on emerging new evidence.

A flexible governance process allows the integration of new concerns and findings in a transparent, fair and fast manner, by regularly feedback to and collection of feedback from all participating stakeholders, using methods provided by the NRGF core functions for communication.

G1. How essential are these teaching goals for a comprehensive understanding of risk governance?

- *very essential*
- *essential*
- *not essential*
- *don't know*

G2. What is your most important teaching goal at this point?

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open question

G3. Monitoring and Feedback: How well is the NRGF process / NANORIGO Portal aligned with your teaching goal?

- *very well aligned*
- *aligned*
- *not aligned*
- *don't know*

G4. Monitoring and Feedback: How supportive is the NRGF process / NANORIGO portal to prepare for your training session?

Efficiency (less time consuming, more cost effective)

- *very supportive*
- *supportive*
- *not supportive*
- *don't know*

Effectivity (complete, consistent, state of the art training)

- *very supportive*
- *supportive*
- *not supportive*
- *don't know*

Section H: Your experience

H1. What is your primary target audience for training activities?

- *Young scientists*
- *Researchers*
- *Regulators*
- *Public*
- *Trainers*
- *Manufacturers*
- *Workers*
- *Insurers*
- *Other*

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H2. For the preparation of nanosafety and nanorisk governance training: Which public resources do / would you use, if any?

open question

H3. Do you know the NANORIGO Nanotechnology Risk Governance Framework portal?

- *I have already utilized it*
- *I have heard about it*
- *I don't*

4.2. Survey evaluation

25 persons participated in the survey. Their answers (as they were given without correcting/amending writing errors or else) are summarized in the following chapter.

Section A: General Questions

A1. Training in the context of nanosafety research: From your point of view, what are the most important teaching goals in regard to a risk governance training for young scientists?

We clustered the answers (as they were given without correcting/amending writing errors or else) into seven categories. The most important teaching goals that were mentioned are:

Understanding risk governance

- *To promote the understanding that risk governance goes far beyond risk assessment.*
- *The message, that risk governance is more than risk assessment and that opinions of different stakeholders have to be considered in order to achieve highly accepted decisions.*
- *which dimensions does risk governance include*
- *difference between government and governance*
- *non-natural-science perspectives*
- *Raising awareness on the complexity and trans-disciplinary and multi-stakeholder nature of risks, on existing uncertainties and how to address them in a most practical, transparent and understandable, and science-based way and in compliance with regulatory requirements*
- *Risk governance is about more than only a technical risk assessment*
- *Understanding the transdisciplinary and multi-stakeholder aspects of risk governance; taking under account impacts on society on concrete examples*

Risk governance increases quality of scientific assessment

- *To ensure the an independent but also fit for purpose scientific assessment, and the communication to risk managers and decision makers.*

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- *weighting risks and benefits of a nanoproduct for society*
- *to generate scientifically sound and regulatory solid procedures for data quality and availability supplemented by application of current tools that aid their interpretation*

Risk governance involves stakeholder opinions

- *The message that risk governance is more than risk assessment and that opinions of different stakeholders have to be considered in order to achieve highly accepted decisions.*
- *Raising awareness on the complexity and trans-disciplinary and multi-stakeholder nature of risks, on existing uncertainties and how to address them in a most practical, transparent and understandable, and science-based way and in compliance with regulatory requirements*
- *Understanding the transdisciplinary and multi-stakeholder aspects of risk governance; taking under account impacts on society on concrete examples*
- *to raise awareness for the societal perspective of risk governance*

Importance of communication (of decisions)

- *To ensure the an independent but also fit for purpose scientific assessment, and the communication to risk managers and decision makers.*
- *communication skills*
- *Be open for weak signals*
- *Understanding the transdisciplinary and multi-stakeholder aspects of risk governance; taking under account impacts on society on concrete examples*
- *the ability to communicate effectively to a wide group of stakeholders - including civil society and non-NT business*

Risk governance process

- *Depends on the type of participants (and their background), but generally to explain the process of risk governance, the challenges related to nanotechnology (available methods, TG and GD, limit reference values, available data), and how it's interlinked with research, industry and other stakeholders.*
- *What is risk management and how to determine the needed risk management measures*
- *to overview the process thinking how to implement risk governance*

Challenges of Nanotechnology

- *Depends on the type of participants (and their background), but generally to explain the process of risk governance, the challenges related to nanotechnology (available methods, TG and GD, limit reference values, available data), and how it's interlinked with research, industry and other stakeholders.*
- *demonstrate differences between chemicals and nanomaterials in terms of risk assessment*
- *Identification of the sources of risk*
- *How to determine hazard of nanomaterials and risk*
- *Raising awareness on the complexity and trans-disciplinary and multi-stakeholder nature of risks, on existing uncertainties and how to address them in a most practical,*

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transparent and understandable, and science-based way and in compliance with regulatory requirements

Get practice how to do risk governance

- *To showcase how the concepts of risk governance and associated tools/methods could be practically applied. This is to assure that the training is not just about sharing info but to enable young scientists to improve their work thanks to the training, having, therefore, long-term impact.*
- *Raising awareness on the complexity and trans-disciplinary and multi-stakeholder nature of risks, on existing uncertainties and how to address them in a most practical, transparent and understandable, and science-based way and in compliance with regulatory requirements*
- *Raising awareness on the complexity and trans-disciplinary and multi-stakeholder nature of risks, on existing uncertainties and how to address them in a most practical, transparent and understandable, and science-based way and in compliance with regulatory requirements*

A2. Training in the context of nanosafety research: From your point of view, what are the most important elements of a risk governance framework?

For the following statistical evaluation, we applied the first three highest ranked answers from each participant and weighted according to the ranking position (1-3).

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Figure 16. Most important elements of a risk governance framework

From trainers' point of view and in the context of nanosafety research the most important elements of a risk governance framework that were highlighted are (1) a handy risk governance process description, (2) a user-friendly guidance through the framework and lagging far behind (3) the availability of e-learning content and an easy to locate access point.

Section B – G Questions to the six steps of NANORIGO risk governance process

The answers of all participants for all single choice questions in section B – G, representing the sections for the six NRGF steps, are summarized in the following Figure 17.

Each of the sections were prefaced by the steps' most important teaching goals from trainer's point of view.

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Questions 1, 3, 4 for section B - G

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Figure 17. Evaluation of the six steps of NANORIGO risk governance process

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In question 1 of each section / NRGF step the participants had to evaluate the importance of the teaching goals for a comprehensive understanding of risk governance. Step 1 (pre-assessment) to step 4 (evaluation) were graded “very essential” or “essential”, and decreased importance for step 5 (management) and least importance for step 6 (monitoring & feedback) was noted. In this regard participants evaluated pre-assessment (73.3%) and evaluation (61.5%) as most essential steps for training.

Question 3 of each section / NRGF addressed the alignment of the NRGF process with the teaching goal. Only the teaching goals of step 1, pre-assessment and step 4, evaluation got a grade “very well aligned” (6.7% and 7.7%, respectively). Step 1, pre-assessment to step 5, management were predominantly evaluated as at least “essential” (47% - 54%).

Question 4 addressed supportiveness (efficiency and effectivity) of the NRGF process / NANORIGO portal to prepare for a training session. In general efficiency was better or equal graded than effectivity (up to 13.3% higher grading). The grade “very supportive” was assigned rarely (even more often for effectivity than efficiency). Between 46.7% to 60% of participants graded “very supportive” and “supportive”, with the exception of step 3 (opinion & concern assessment) and step 6 (monitoring & feedback), which received just 31%- 38% of these gradings.

Question 2 for section B – G: What is the most important teaching goal at this point

The participants were asked for each individual NRGF step about their most important teaching goal.

B2. Pre-assessment

We clustered the answers into eight categories. Regarding the pre-assessment step, the participants saw as most important teaching goals the following aspects:

Key aim of this step is “Framing of the risk”

- *A proper problem formulation*
- *A missing or wrong framing of the risk may go along with inferior outcomes and inappropriate decisions in risk governance*
- *showing the scope of potential risks and associated concerns (social, environmental, economic etc.)*
- *Identifying all relevant actors and problematics*
- *clarity and policy implications*

Pre-assessment is the key step in the risk governance process

- *Pre-assessment is the key step, which decides about the following risk governance process and decisions. Wrong appraisal at this point can lead to "wrong" decisions later.*

Step for avoiding wrong decisions

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- *Pre-assessment is the key step, which decides about the following risk governance process and decisions. Wrong appraisal at this point can lead to "wrong" decisions later.*
- *Understanding objectively the risk level after guidance to risk governance*

Explain “what is risk governance”, the aim of pre-assessment step and its mechanisms

- *To explain what risk governance is and how the mechanisms exactly work (responsibilities of regulators, different regulatory bodies in different sectors, governmental bodies) as this is not my professional background*
- *A general understanding of the risk assessment*
- *to understand what pre-assessment serves and that it enables initiating the process*

Awareness for different views / stakeholders

- *to raise awareness for different views and that each view and opinion is equally considered in all subsequent steps*
- *showing the scope of potential risks and associated concerns (social, environmental, economic etc.)*
- *Identifying all relevant actors and problematics*

Get practice in the process (how to perform pre-assessment step)

- *How to perform a good pre-assessment step*

Risk of Nanotechnology considering the whole product life cycle

- *Envision the complete life cycle of the nano-product: what is the function of nano and why is it needed? What will happen to the nanomaterials during use and end of life? Who will use the products and who will get exposed at end-of-life treatment? Could there be possible abuses and unintended treatments that may cause exposures at unexpected places?*

Policy implications

- *clarity and policy implications*

C2. Technical/Scientific Assessment

We clustered the answers in seven categories. Regarding the technical/scientific assessment step, the participants saw as most important teaching goals the following aspects:

Where to find information

- *We have detailed and updated guidance in EFSA for dietary exposure*

Understand complexity of a risk

- *To understand that risk may appear as be simple, complex or uncertain and finally ambiguous, despite all effort for a proper technical assessment*

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- *risk = exposure / effect*
- *the importance of the specifics of the domain*

To transfer knowledge about content of this step

- *To collect current scientific knowledge based on all available tools, data, studies and to identify knowledge gaps.*
- *To explain the methods behind these steps and their regulatory acceptance*
- *data availability and tool integration in a user-friendly manner, guidance to relevant sources of information*

To transfer knowledge about aim / purpose of this step

- *To explain the methods behind these steps and their regulatory acceptance*

Quality assessment of available information

- *quality assessment of available data*

Understand process step (how, what, for whom)

- *How to perform a risk assessment*
- *based on the pre-assessment, access to relevant data and tools is given and how to use them to address the various types of risks and stakeholders needs and concerns involved*
- *This teaching aspects depend on the target group. It does not make much sense to teach too much details in hazard assessment to people, who have not the decision-making power regarding the design and application of nano-products. These aspects of Risk assessment should be thought merely to expert's grade decision makers (tech-developers, designers, procurement staff) - but not in a too much academic way. Teaching scientific assessment methods should be limited to Environmental / occupational health managers.*

Only suitable for a limited training target group

- *This teaching aspects depend on the target group. It does not make much sense to teach too much details in hazard assessment to people, who have not the decision-making power regarding the design and application of nano-products. These aspects of Risk assessment should be thought merely to expert's grade decision makers (tech-developers, designers, procurement staff) - but not in an too much academic way. Teaching scientific assessment methods should be limited to Environmental / occupational health managers.*

D2. Opinion & Concern Assessment

We clustered the answers in five categories. Regarding the opinion & concern step, the participants saw as most important teaching goals the following aspects:

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Is different from scientific risk assessment

- *This is essential, but should be separated from the scientific risk assessment in order to avoid interference in the assessment of scientific evidence*

Include different stakeholder's perceptions and opinions!

- *To understand that there are different stakeholders with different risk perception and knowledge out in the universe. Despite conflicting interests, all these have to be considered and inclusion is an active step and needs appropriate action*
- *To illustrate the importance of identifying and including all stakeholders' opinions.*
- *Raise awareness on different stakeholders' opinions, perceptions, and concerns.*
- *Identification of the social, environmental and economic concerns*
- *To involve and inform all relevant stakeholders about the regulatory, economic and social context and to communicate both benefits and concerns in an easily understandable and transparent way*
- *understanding of how to understand and capture the phenomena of "concern"*
- *to raise awareness for societal inclusion and teach ways on how to interact with stakeholders*

Understanding risk governance

- *demonstrate the benefits of risk governance over the traditional risk assessment*

Understand process step (how, what, for whom)

- *same as previous answer: teaching of experts - its more an issue of corporate culture to engage with stakeholders and how. Addressing policy makers is important, but merely in an outcome-oriented manner*
- *understanding of how to understand and capture the phenomena of "concern"*

Only suitable for a limited training target group

- *same as previous answer: teaching of experts - its more an issue of corporate culture to engage with stakeholders and how. Addressing policy makers is important, but merely in an outcome-oriented manner*

E2. Evaluation:

We clustered the answers in four categories. Regarding the evaluation step, the participants saw as most important teaching goals the following aspects:

To transfer knowledge about content of this step

- *In my view it should be essential to clarify these two processes in training for young researchers*

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- *The term is confusing for risk assessors, as we use risk characterization as the term for comparing hazard and exposure and estimate the likelihood and magnitude of the effects (final step in the risk assessment process). Acceptability and mitigation options involve risk managers and are the next step.*
- *Evaluation prepares the final decision, which could be done by outside stakeholders, such as regulators or responsible persons within industry or institutions. Thus, the propositions/recommendations in this step are of major importance.*
- *How to evaluate appropriately considering the different bit and pieces from the different steps.*
- *Balanced weighing of and taking all facts and scenarios duly into account based on scientific data, but also on the particular perception and acceptance of risks of all involved stakeholders and the implementation of the precautionary principle*

Understand process step (how, what, for whom)

- *That risk evaluation has to include the results of all three preceding steps and that risk classification is an important factor at this point.*
- *How to evaluate appropriately considering the different bit and pieces from the different steps.*
- *How to integrate all the aspects of risk to give a final evaluation*
- *understanding risk metrics*

Communication of strategies to stakeholders

- *proper communication of the respective risk mitigation strategies to all stakeholders involved*

Integration of all aspects

- *See the whole picture and have a full understanding of the societal impact of risks*
- *to weigh effective measures with values reflected by different stakeholder groups*

F2. Management

We clustered the answers in four categories. Regarding the management step, the participants saw as most important teaching goals the following aspects:

Only suitable for a limited training target group

- *I do not see this as essential for training young researchers, general knowledge on risk management options should be sufficient.*
- *This step is obviously essential for training decision makers*

Understand range of possible actions

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- *To understand the range of possible actions for management of risk. From acceptance with specific regulations to averting the risk by banning a product.*
- *Hierarchy of control in risk management*

Integration of all stakeholders and perspectives

- *To illustrate that risk management has to act responsibly to all stakeholders and to make realize the pros and cons of the precautionary principle.*
- *life-cycle perspective*
- *Here, transparent and up to date risk communication is important to arrive at good decision-making and conflict solution according to stakeholder expectations and the type and scope of risks and the potential to avoid, reduce or mitigate them*
- *how does risk governance relate to wider public policy*

Understand process step (how, what, for whom)

- *How to do a risk management plan*
- *to aid customers in their management implementation, to provide guidance based on documents and valid current and updated information resources*

G2. Monitoring & Feedback

We clustered the answers in four categories. Regarding the monitoring & feedback step, the participants saw as most important teaching goals the following aspects:

To transfer knowledge about content of this step

- *As follow-up of the risk characterization, scientists need to indicate monitoring options (for exposure, for hazards and if possible for risk)*
- *To understand that risk has a life cycle. The risk governance must not end as long as the risk associated product is in the market or still in use. Regulations have to consider and define all follow up measures in advance, once the risk/product is accepted.*

Understanding risk governance

- *To understand that risk has a life cycle. The risk governance must not end as long as the risk associated product is in the market or still in use. Regulations have to consider and define all follow up measures in advance, once the risk/product is accepted.*
- *Risk governance does not end with a decision. We talk about a life cycle.*
- *ensuring risk governance is dynamic and iterative*
- *to understand how the feedback loop aids future challenges and optimize the risk governance cycle*

Importance of risk governance step

- *To my feeling right now, maybe the least important subtopic*

Get practice how to do risk governance and process step

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- *knowledge on monitoring strategies: how is done practically?*
- *Providing and combining risk governance tools and the necessary high-quality data with innovation on how to implement a continuous monitoring strategy that ensures compliance of a given situation (manufacture, use and disposal of NM and the occupational/consumer/environmental setting) with agreed decision-making and current and future legislation, regulation that addresses in particular the concerns and needs of stakeholders including the public*

Section H Your Experience

To evaluate participant's answers appropriately they were asked about their experience.

H1. What is your primary training audience for training activities?

The primary training audience for the survey participants were young scientists, researchers and public (Figure 18).

Figure 18. Primary training audience for training activities.

H2. For the preparation of nanosafety and nanorisk governance training: Which public resources do / would you use, if any?

We clustered the answers in three categories. The participants would use the following public resources:

Regulations

- *EFSA Nano guidance and recent EFSA scientific opinions for dietary risk and food safety*

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- *ECHA guidance for nanoforms (once are finally updated) for non-dietary exposures and environmental risk assessments.*
- *ECHA*
- *REACH*

(It was unclear to me why for a case study on TiO₂ as food additive the presentation focused on the ECHA classification for inhalation instead of the EFSA assessment as food additive.)

EU projects

- *IRGC resources*
- *IRGC process*
- *other Horizon2020 projects*
- *appropriate EU funding*
- *outputs from EU project and scientific papers*
- *training resources generated by the NMBP projects provided by the NSC WG-A*
- *Resources & tutorials available on the portal*

Scientific papers

- *outputs from EU project and scientific papers*
- *mostly scientific publications, and examples for risk governance processes, e.g., MSC*
- *scientific publications. Publicly accessible guidelines and databases (e.g., OECD-WPMN)*

To sum it up, the survey participants (would) use for their preparation of nanosafety and nanorisk governance training materials about guidance papers and regulations, outputs from EU projects and scientific papers. In conclusion, none of them had access to an existing comprehensive and central framework, where trainers can find all necessary links and documents.

H3. Do you know the NANORIGO Nanotechnology Risk Governance Framework portal?

About 40% of the survey participants had already utilized the NANORIGO NRGF portal, about 55% had heard about it (Figure 19), hence more than 50% of the participants could not evaluate the features and quality of the portal.

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Figure 19. Knowledge about NRGF

5. Survey on NRGF – early career researchers

As described in chapter 2, early career researchers were asked to fill out a survey after training program participation, aiming at getting information on perception of the helpfulness of an NRGF. In the master students' group – Salzburg 40 participants voted, in the young scientists' group – Venice 15 participants.

A. Problem identification

The first section of the questionnaire aimed at attuning the participants and at evaluating their appreciation concerning the ambiguity of the 'TiO₂ case' and, how risk governance could support informed decision making.

1. How did concerns in regard of TiO₂ come into being?

Both early career researcher groups grasped the specific problematic associated with the 'TiO₂ case' (Table 2). The student group - Salzburg provided more detailed comments due to more insight in the case because their training program included a more intensive engagement with the case (preparation of synopsis and key publication presentation; presentation to all participants).

Table 2. Understanding of the 'TiO₂ case'

Master students - Salzburg	Young scientists & experts - Venice
<i>A French agency claimed that it should no longer be considered safe</i>	<i>readily available nano material, so this was chosen</i>
<i>A growing TiO₂ industry lead to research being done about its effects on animals/humans</i>	<i>From presentation; seriously I didn't know about it before</i>
<i>As it is designated as carcinogens by international agency</i>	<i>In vivo tests about potential risks</i>
<i>Because in one study (Bettini et al. 2017) they found out that there were formed aberrant crypt foci in male rats and also that there may be some problems at the reproductivity.</i>	<i>Due the amounts being produced; increased exposure</i>
<i>Because of the study of Bettini et al.</i>	<i>French concerns</i>
<i>Because risk of certain additives/chemicals is regularly evaluated</i>	<i>In vivo results that showed potential carcinogenicity</i>

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<i>Bettini</i>	<i>large production</i>
<i>Cancerogenesis</i>	<i>New information on nanoparticles</i>
<i>Classification type</i>	<i>Society</i>
<i>Concerning study results</i>	<i>Nanoscale considerations</i>
<i>Due to genotoxicity</i>	
<i>Effects and how to deal with it</i>	
<i>EFSA study showed some adverse effects</i>	
<i>Exposure of mice to high doses of TiO₂ lead to inflammatory effects</i>	
<i>Health issues</i>	
<i>It's a NP used for a long time in a lot of stuff and was never really tested before being implemented that's why they wanted to test it.</i>	
<i>May be cancerous</i>	
<i>Murine studies</i>	
<i>Often used food additive and nobody really knew why it is used and what it causes in the body</i>	
<i>Other NPs, new field so delayed concerns</i>	
<i>people especially working in factories had health problems</i>	
<i>Possible cancer induction; high toxicity</i>	
<i>Scientific studies conducted in the 70s (inhalation) and 2016 (oral uptake).</i>	
<i>Showed up in studies</i>	
<i>Some illnesses after consuming a product which contains TiO₂</i>	
<i>Studies performed</i>	
<i>Studies showing negative health effects on intestine (Bettini et al. 2017); no developmental and reproductive testing was done; studies on mice showed possible neurotoxicity</i>	
<i>TiO₂ has been classified by the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) as an IARC Group 2B</i>	
<i>To find out if it is cancerous; studies on rodents about TiO₂ inhalation and as food additive</i>	
<i>With food</i>	
<i>With the general concern of nanoparticles, the possible toxicity of TiO₂ raised</i>	

2. Who was initially involved in raising concerns towards TiO₂?

Both early career researcher groups decided for authorities/regulators, scientists and risk assessors as the most involved stakeholders in raising concerns towards TiO₂ and identified correctly the public's involvement as too late for a well-accepted decision. (Figure 20).

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Figure 20. Involved stakeholders in concerns towards TiO₂.

3. What is to say about the scientific evidence for TiO₂ hazard?

Both early career researcher groups identified ambiguous results on TiO₂ toxicity studies and stated that more information is needed for the correct classification of TiO₂ (Table 3). The student group - Salzburg provided more detailed comments because their training program included a more intensive preoccupation with the case (preparation of synopsis and key publication presentation; presentation to all participants).

Table 3. Scientific evidence for TiO₂ hazard

Master students - Salzburg	Young scientists & experts - Venice
<i>Ambiguous results. As for inhalation very shady, more evidence for potential risk when orally consumed</i>	<i>The studies were not carried out in a way that is appropriate for nano materials. But it can also not be excluded that there is a hazard.</i>
<i>Carcinogenic</i>	<i>INCONCLUSIVE</i>
<i>Classified as B1 as a food additive.</i>	<i>FAIR data</i>
<i>Clear</i>	<i>No evidence that is non-hazardous</i>
<i>could eventually be genotoxic - more research is needed!!</i>	<i>Insufficient information to demonstrate safety</i>
<i>Harmful tendencies confirmed, long-term studies needed, risk not worth the gain</i>	<i>there are a lot of published research papers in ingestion and inhalation</i>
<i>Inflammatory reactions</i>	<i>enough for knowledge-based decisions</i>
<i>Inflammatory reactions in rats</i>	<i>There is a hazard with particles <30nm</i>
<i>It is not all too reliable</i>	<i>Inhalation/ingestion of Tio2 may cause carcinogenic effects</i>
<i>It's an open question</i>	<i>Cytotoxic; carcinogenic through inhalation</i>
<i>lack of transparency, no harmonized hazard classes</i>	<i>Carcinogenic</i>
<i>lung cancer, epithelial lesions but not significant results</i>	<i>It was not possible yet to rule out the concerns</i>
<i>maybe genotoxic but lead not to a mutation, but definitely more research has to be done</i>	
<i>More validation required</i>	
<i>No clear evidence of harm, shape and size more important than material</i>	
<i>no proper evidence</i>	

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No uniform result	
None, uncertainty	
Not clear as its only tested in rats	
Not proven in humans	
not safe	
Not very consistent	
Potentially cancerogenic	
Suspected to cause cancer	
there is no real evidence - maybe for the inhaling way	
There is no scientific evidence.	
There is some about without follow up	
TiO ₂ is potentially carcinogenic but further studies are necessary	
Toxicity, cancer researcher on mice	

4. What decision was taken in the end for the EU

The majority of early career researchers captured the most important decisions made in the 'TiO₂ case' (Figure 21).

Figure 21. Final decision taken for the EU concerning the TiO₂ case.

5. If any societal stakeholders' concerns arise: Should the precautionary principle prevail responsible innovation?

The distribution of answers concerning the precautionary principle was quite equal for both early career researcher groups. About 50% of them would decide for the precautionary principle only if a risk cannot be properly managed, 30% would always prefer it and 20% would follow public opinion. None of them decided for the option "innovation should always prevail". This indicates that the participants became quite sensitive on how important it is to include society in the risk governance process.

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Figure 22. Appraisal of the precautionary principle.

B. The 'TiO₂ case' in the context NRGF process

Section B aimed at evaluating whether conduct of the training enables to bring the TiO₂ case into the context of the risk governance process. In this regard, early career researchers were asked questions to the process steps one to five (Figure 23).

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Figure 23. Placement of the 'TiO₂ case' within the risk governance process. Numbering refers to the question numbers of the questions catalogue listed in chapter 4 (Self)Assessment.

In this section the distribution of answers differed between both early career researcher groups due to their different education and different intensity of having been introduced to the 'TiO₂ case'.

Both groups categorized the case as "not simple", but predominantly as "uncertain". However, in contrast to the young scientists – Venice, master students – Salzburg with detailed preoccupation with several key studies rated it to 26% as "ambiguous". Whereas most master students - Salzburg did not perceive that sufficient scientific information about TiO₂ NPs' hazards, exposure and vulnerability of affected populations was available (60%), most young scientists – Venice believed that (strong or moderate believe; 79%). Most early career

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researchers were convinced that the involvement of affected stakeholders and society was not sufficient and early enough in the 'TiO₂ case', the master students' group – Salzburg (68%) more than the young scientists' group – Venice (50%). Excluding option "don't know", most early career researchers thought (strong, moderate believe) that accepted criteria by science and society have been applied for reviewing and weighing the synthesized base for later decision making (master students – Salzburg: 63.7%; young scientists – Venice: 77.8%). Concerning the question whether in the 'TiO₂ case' the management action 'TiO₂ food ban' was the only option to avoid, retain or transfer the risk, the answers of the young scientists were quite inverse, which may be again explained by their different prior knowledge and prearrangement. Most of the master students – Salzburg (56%) saw additional other options, whereas 77% did not see them. Overall, more researchers in the young scientists' group – Venice, decided for the option "don't know" than in the master student group – Salzburg.

C. Advantage in using NRGF

Section C addressed the evaluation of the NRGF by polling the opinion about its advantage related to risk governance process steps one to five (Figure 24).

Both early career researcher groups saw an advantage in using NRGF for framing the risk (step 1), with 97% in the master students' group – Salzburg and 92% in the young scientists' group – Venice ("strong advantage", "moderate advantage"; most of them "strong advantage"). A similar picture was observed for the advantage of using NRGF looking at the other process steps: (step 2) scientific assessment with 90% in the master student group – Salzburg and 92% in the young scientists group – Venice ("strong advantage", "moderate advantage"; most of them "strong advantage"), (step 3) opinion & concern assessment with 90% in the master students group – Salzburg and 86% in the young scientists group – Venice ("strong advantage", "moderate advantage"; most of the master students group – Salzburg: "strong advantage"), (step 4) evaluation with 95% in the master students group – Salzburg and 93% in the young scientists group – Venice ("strong advantage", "moderate advantage"), and (step 5) management with 89% in the master students group – Salzburg and 92% in the young scientists group – Venice ("strong advantage", "moderate advantage"; most of the master students group – Salzburg: "strong advantage").

In summary, all early career researchers appreciated the advantage of each risk governance process step.

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Figure 24. Risk governance process steps evaluation. Numbering refers to the question numbers of the questions catalogue listed in chapter 4 (Self)Assessment.

D. Overall NRGF benefits

The last section D of the questionnaire aimed at evaluation of the overall NRGF benefits.

16. For you as young scientist: What are the most important elements of a risk governance framework?

In a first question early career researchers were asked about the most important elements of a risk governance framework. Both groups evaluated the “E-learning content” as the most relevant element. The master students’ group – Salzburg ranked on position 2 the “user-friendly guidance” through the framework and on position 3 the “tool collection”. The young scientists’

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group – Venice ranked on position 2 the “data collection” and on position 3, equally, “tool collection” and “communication platform”.

Figure 25. Elements of risk governance framework ranking.

17. For you as young scientist: Do you think that the regulatory outcome of the ‘TiO₂ case’ would have been different given that such a risk governance process with all steps would have been applied early?

The final question aimed at evaluating the NRGF potential to affect decisions. Most early career researchers, at least moderately, attributed this influence to the framework with 84% in the master students group – Salzburg and 75% in the young scientists group – Venice.

Figure 26. Risk governance framework potential to affect decisions.

In conclusion, early career researchers rated the NRGF as a whole as well as its single steps as helpful to perform risk governance and to reach good and well-accepted decisions for a rational, the risk class adjusted dealing with NM. Interestingly, they rated the single steps better (predominantly “strong believe”) than the framework as a whole (predominantly moderate

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believe). To achieve this, they saw an E-learning offer, followed by a user-friendly guidance through the framework, as the most important element of an NRGF.

The differences in preparatory knowledge and qualification of the to participant groups and the different training program unveiled its influence on their advantage rating.

6. Interim NRGF Web-platform validation for WP3: CS1 user experience feedback

In July 2021, WP3 initiated an interim NRGF Web-platform validation. The full questionnaire including the grading (marked in yellow) and textual answers from CS1 (Task T5.1) point of view can be found in Appendix 6. The grading scheme was defined by WP3. The grading was derived from functional assessment by CS1 beta users of the platform prototype. The grading of application quality requested in individual sections is summarized in Table 4.

Table 4. Grading of NRGF application quality

Section	NRGF step	Question	Grading
Information & contents	general	correct, well written, relevant to purpose	★ ★ ★
	general	complete but concise	★ ★ ★
	general	visual explanation of concepts	★ ★ ★ ★
	general	information from reliable source	★ ★ ★ ★ ★
Individual funct. assessment	preassessment	define issue and frame boundaries	★ ★ ★
	technical scientific assessment	distinction of tool types	★ ★ ★ ★
	technical scientific assessment	quality and quantity of tools	★ ★ ★ ★
	technical scientific assessment	explanation for tools	★ ★ ★ ★
	opinion and concern assessment	quality and quantity of tools	★ ★ ★ ★
	opinion and concern assessment	explanation for tools	★ ★ ★ ★
	evaluation	quality and quantity of tools	★ ★ ★ ★
	evaluation	explanation for tools	★ ★ ★ ★
	management	quality and quantity of tools	★ ★ ★ ★
	management	explanation for tools	★ ★ ★ ★
	other tools	offer of additional links to other tools	★ ★ ★
	monitoring and feedback	under construction	
communication platform	under construction		
Adequacy	general	content set (info., tools, links, guidelines, communication)	★ ★ ★
	general	visualization, language design of content	★ ★ ★ ★
Usability	landing home page	usefulness	★ ★ ★ ★
	general	manual	★ ★ ★ ★
	general	easy to learn to use	★ ★ ★ ★ ★
	general	menu labels, icons, instructions	★ ★ ★ ★
	general	movement between screens	★ ★ ★ ★
	general	availability of necessary links	★ ★ ★ ★
	general	tabs, swipes, pinches, scrolls	★ ★ ★ ★
	general	consistence of components and screens	★ ★ ★
Design	general	size of buttons, icons, menus, screen content	★ ★ ★ ★
	general	quality /resolution of graphics used	★ ★ ★ ★
	general	appealing web-platform	★ ★ ★
Personal evaluation	general	appropriate, coherent, integrated practical reflection of NRGF	★ ★ ★
	general	recommendation to other colleagues	★ ★ ★ ★
	general	use on regular basis to carry out nano risk related tasks	★ ★ ★ ★
	general	overall rating	★ ★ ★ ★

1	strongly agree
2	agree
3	neither agree nor disagree
4	disagree
5	strongly disagree

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At this point CS1 assigned an overall rating for the application of three (of maximum five) stars with the attached main comments /advice:

- Missing comprehensive introduction in the general principles of nanorisk governance process
- Missing visual context
- Pre-assessment: the contentual decisions to be made here are in a black box from a user perspective with no information about consequences
- Data aspect is hidden
- Trainer role is not part of the presumed nanotechnology value chain

7. Beyond training: Discursive formation and better decision making - an experience report from UL

Social discourse with broad stakeholders' inclusion may promote better decision making, allowing the adaption of societal stakeholders' perception by learning and thus, may help to balance risks and benefits associated with nanotechnology. These forms of intervention may go beyond traditional concepts of topic focussed and target group centered training. Here, UL reports on such an experience, complementing our case study on training.

The Classification, Labelling and Packaging (CLP) classification process of TiO₂ was a use case on how to apply the NANORIGO Nano Risk Governance Framework (NRGF) elaborated within the NMBP-13 cluster to define a type of risk and respond on the proposed classifications (CS on TiO₂, D5.7). Specifically, the following points have been addressed in the discussion: 1) how the NRGF could support the CLP regulatory process in the future, 2) whether any steps of the NRGF are missing or not conducted optimally, and 3) how NRGF could define the type of risk. This issue has been examined by applying the Data Readiness Levels (DRLs; referred to as Knowledge, information, and data Readiness Levels [KaRLs] in this report) elaborated within D1.7 of the NANORIGO Project to each step of the NRGF process (Figure 27).

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Figure 27. Knowledge, Information, and Data Readiness Levels (KaRLs) for risk assessment, communication and governance of nano- and other advanced materials as elaborated within Task 1.7 of the NANORIGO project.

The aim and mission of the training was to support, allow, and contribute to discursive formation. The case study on TiO₂ CLP has identified that the large number of comments provided at the time of the public consultation period for the CLH report on TiO₂ did not get response from or discussion with ECHA and the Committee for Risk Assessment (RAC). Of relevance to scientists is the realization that the massive amounts of scientific data being generated are not being adequately synthesized and presented in a form that is easily accessible and usable to government regulatory bodies.

The training followed by a discussion showed that knowledge classification about risk is one of the most crucial steps, as it defines the type of participation, actions, and discourse. Within the NANORIGO Project, the NRGCC or house-like entity could make use of the KaRL system and other tools developed in WP1 and WP2 to support CLP and similar regulatory processes by bringing scientific sources (data, information, and knowledge along with tools) and problem owners (e.g., industry, regulators, and the public sphere) to the same table for discursive engagement to elaborate more solutions that could be proposed to decision makers.

Based on the analyses CLP process for TiO₂, the process is suited for simple risk problems (Renn, 2008, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4020-6799-0_1). This class of risk problems requires hardly any deviation from traditional decision-making. Data is provided by statistical analysis, goals are determined by law or statutory requirements and the role of risk management is to ensure that all risk reduction measures are implemented and enforced. Traditional risk-risk comparisons (or risk-risk trade-offs), risk-benefit analysis and cost-effectiveness studies are the instruments of choice for finding the most appropriate risk reduction measures. Additionally, risk managers can rely on best practice and, in cases of low

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impact, on trial and error. The major issues here are that the potential negative consequences are obvious, the values that are applied are non-controversial and the remaining uncertainties low.

The characterization of a particular risk depends on the degree of difficulty of establishing the cause-effect relationship between a risk agent and its potential consequences, the reliability of the relationship, and the value system in place. For each category, a strategy is then derived for risk assessment and risk management, as well as the level and form of stakeholder participation, supported by proposals for appropriate methods and tools for a targeted risk management strategy. For example, 'simple' risk problems can be managed using a 'routine-based' strategy and traditional decision-making instruments (instrumental discourse). Other categories need a broader societal discourse to enable participative decision making

However, the TiO₂ classification could not be classified as a simple risk problem due to different perspectives on the risk and how likely and severe potential adverse outcomes may be. Therefore, the TiO₂ risk should be classified as complex, uncertain or even ambiguous risks. Uncertain risks or Ambiguous risk problems require a participatory 'discourse-based' strategy aiming to create tolerance and mutual understanding of conflicting views and values with a view to eventually reconciling them (Florin & Bürkler, 2017, <https://doi.org/10.5075/epfl-irgc-233739>; Renn & Roco, 2006, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11051-006-9092-7>). But to assure the participatory 'discourse-based' strategy a new inclusive approach is needed for consensus building and decision proposing.

Key take-aways from our exercise and discussion on TiO₂ CLP

1. TiO₂ CLP regulation is not a simple problem, but complex according to IRGC risk governance scheme! Consequently not 'instrumental discourse' but reflective discourse is perhaps a right choice! The outcome of discussion is that interested groups are not familiar with the concepts of risks being either simple, complex, uncertain, or ambiguous (Renn, 2008, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4020-6799-0_1). NRGF could thus support / enable interested groups to understand a type of risk. NRGF supports sharing knowledge and information (as well as access to data) when needed that is science based and include the knowledge readiness (KaRL) levels assessment as a tool for risk governance.

2. Training and discussion on TiO₂ CLP regulation process **identified that** a need for *social innovation* where initiate a **broader societal discourse** to enable participative decision making. The NRGF or house-like entity could make use of the KaRL system and other similar tools could support CLP and similar regulatory processes by bringing scientific sources (data, information, and knowledge along with tools) and problem owners (e.g., industry, regulators, and the public sphere) to the same table to elaborate more solutions that could be proposed to decision makers.

8. Conclusions

The outcome of this case study, CS1, provides evidence that the NANORIGO NRGF is a viable instrument to support knowledge acquisition, enhancing the basic as well deep understanding on the needs and benefits of a nanorisk governance process and, thus, is very supportive for stakeholders dealing with tasks of risk governance beyond simple risk assessment. The benefit of applying the NANORIGO NRGF was confirmed for stakeholders with a specific perspective and needs in the role of training providers, as well as individuals in the position of trainees, gathering knowledge of and first experience with the nanorisk governance landscape, its principles, processes, tools and data collections.

From the trainers' point of view and in the context of nanosafety research the most important elements of a risk governance framework are (1) a handy risk governance process description, (2) a user-friendly guidance through the framework and lagging far behind (3) the availability of e-learning content and an easy to locate access point. About 40% of survey participants (training providers) confirmed that they have already used the NANORIGO NRGF and the NANORIGO portal and that these resources are aligned with their requirements. The NANORIGO NRGF and portal is deemed to be supportive concerning providing training in an efficient manner, however, concerning the effectiveness of the provided resources, a lower degree of consent was expressed. A lower degree of efficient and effective support was reported for the risk governance tasks "opinion & concern assessment" as well as for "monitoring & feedback".

For trainers the NRGF steps 1 – 4 are more important than steps 5 – 6. The most important steps are step 1, pre-assessment and step 4, evaluation. Step 6, monitoring and feedback, is deemed to be the least important element. Step 2, scientific assessment, and step 5, management, are to the most extent of all steps, context-dependent, thus training has to be individualized in any case and trainers' expectations concerning tailored NRGF content is lower.

The feedback of early career researchers surpasses the overall positive impression of the trainers. 90% of early career researchers classified the NRGF process as strongly supportive or moderately supportive, with emphasis on strong support. The most important elements of the risk governance framework for early career researchers are (1) the "e-learning content" and (2) the "user-friendly guidance", "data collections" and "tool collections".

In this regard, the prioritization of most important elements, trainers emphasize the need for a thorough process description along with a user-friendly guidance through the NRGF, while early career researchers are at first looking for content, such as e-learning resources, data and tool collections.

Overall, young scientists, involved in the educational event and role play, analyzing the case of the EU commission "TiO₂ food ban", expressed very strong conviction that applying the

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NANORIGO NRGF would have been beneficial for decision making. This outcome of the case study CS1 provides further evidence for the applicability and usefulness of the NANORIGO NRGF.

9. Appendix

1. The purpose of a risk governance framework (ACHEMA 2021)
2. “Rubber granulate”, a case study for using the framework
3. Illustrating and applying the NANORIGO framework with Smart Nanomaterials
4. Slides for role play “Applying the NANORIGO framework with Smart Nanomaterials”
5. Trainer survey form
6. NRGF Web-platform validation

Appendix 9.1

The purpose of a risk governance framework (ACHEMA 2021)

The Risk Governance Framework

Three EU H2020 projects working together

ACHEMA Pulse, 16th June 2021

Arto Sämänen, Finnish Institute of Occupational Health

Gov4Nano: Grant N°814401
NANORIGO: Grant N°814530
RiskGONE: Grant N°814425

1

Question:

Is it clear to you what purpose the Framework will serve? [yes/no]

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2

Why do we need Risk Governance Framework?

- Have important views of some stakeholders been ignored in the past, which has led to inappropriate decisions?
- Could bad things happen very soon, or in the longer term future?
- What are the risks related to engineered nanomaterials that our current methods and tools are inappropriate to deal with, and which a more systematic and holistic process help deal with?
- What would be needed to address these risks?
- Would a common interdisciplinary and multistakeholder formalized process help? Would a harmonized process help (ie. all stakeholders would be encouraged to use the same)?

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Characteristics of good risk governance (Klinke & Renn, 2019)

1. the new notion of risk governance emphasizes the process of **risk characterization and evaluation** as the core of **legitimate risk decision making**,
 2. an integrative and adaptive concept, especially with regard to **integrating** processes of **risk characterization and evaluation** as a means to **link estimation and management**
 3. an **inclusive and participatory activity** that integrates various **stakeholder perspectives, engages in the co-generation** of practical knowledge
 4. **resolves contingencies by developing discrete scenarios** that **translate different concerns and positions** in **negotiable and communicable narratives**.
- How to assess, analyze, and design processes and institutions that meet the three characteristics outlined above?

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Risk Governance Framework

Governance refers to the actions, processes, traditions and institutions by which authority is exercised and decisions are taken and implemented.

Involves **multi-disciplinary** sciences and **multi-stakeholder** approaches

A **FRAMEWORK** for risk governance is based on a defined and structured **process** to addressing **risk** in a comprehensive and holistic manner.

Marie-Valentine Florin, EPFL for NANORIGO

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Risk Governance Framework

<https://irgc.org/risk-governance/irgc-risk-governance-framework/>

Adaptation and testing to nanotechnology and other advanced materials.

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NANORIGO Risk Governance Framework

Question:

What benefits do you see in our risk governance approach? [open question]

The RGF in practice Nanoparticles in rubber tyres wear and tear as an example

ACHEMA Pulse, 16th June 2021
Arto Säämänen, Finnish Institute of Occupational Health
Mark Morrison, Optimat Ltd.
Pieter van Broekhuizen and Kees Le Blansch, Bureau KLB
Daan Schuurbijs, DPF

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9

**Nanoparticles
released from
rubber tyres?**

Aim of the case study

- The aim of this case study is to **test the Nano Risk Governance Framework** using the issue of ‘nano wear and tear of rubber tyres’ as a test case.
- This is done by **addressing the central issue** (‘nano wear and tear of rubber tyres’) in concertation **with several stakeholder groups**, following the steps and structure of the framework.
- **Focus on how the framework can help and/or improve the governance of the nano risks in society**

Not a *really real* case
 Not a *really real* process
 Stakeholders participate on a voluntary basis and cannot be overburdened

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11

Pre-assessment

- Define issues to be looked at, involve stakeholders and capture current perspectives of risk as well as opportunities and potential strategies for addressing these
- Defining the problem and framing the boundaries – objective and context for risk governance
- Gathering what is already known and is not
- How the risk is framed by different stakeholders

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Involvement of stakeholders

- provide support to make risk governance effective
- make risk communication operational
- engage stakeholders to manage risk according the available knowledge on risks
- emphasizes the role of social, political or economic evaluation relating to the outcome of the risk assessment, before management decisions are taken

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NRGF steps to be covered within this case study

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Question:

Which stakeholder groups should be involved? [word cloud]

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Question:

According to you, is there a problem concerning nano wear and tear of rubber tyres?

- 1. [Vote: yes / no / I don't know]**
- 2. If yes, what is the nature of this problem? [Open question]**

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Stakeholders involved in this case study

1. Associations of tyre manufacturers
2. Association of tyre recyclers
3. Dutch road authorities
4. Trade unions (of road workers and users)
5. Inhabitants of a residential area near highways
6. Tyres manufacturers

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What is the issue?

This project has received funding from The European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant agreement 814530.

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Pre-assessment interviews

- Certain or uncertain?
 - Level of knowledge differs
 - Is it really an issue? Less knowledge - the more uncertain
- Demarcation
 - Release caused by tyres vs. all traffic emissions
- (Nano) Tyre wear (possibly?) in what compartment/media?
 - Off the tyre – off tyre and road – environmental air pollution – air pollution inside the vehicle – groundwater – food chain – microplastic soup

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The ‘Rubber Tyres’ case study

With stakeholders

With NANORIGO partners
(and NMBP13 colleagues)

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Technical risk assessment

- Develop and synthesise the knowledge base for the decision, including prevention, mitigation, adaptation or sharing the risk
- Collect existing information about hazards, exposure and vulnerability (of affected populations and systems) and consequences (in case the risk materialises).
- Perform human and environmental risk assessment; probability of occurrence of harm and severity of consequences must be assessed
- Expert deliberation conducted by epistemic communities and institution

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Opinion, concern and risk perception assessment

- Capture the opinions, perceptions and concerns of affected populations
- Gain knowledge about the perceived causes and consequences (benefits and risks)
- Comprehend the social response to the risk. How do people react?
- Understand drivers of stakeholder behaviour

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Risk management escalator

ACTORS				Civil society
			Affected stakeholders	
TYPE OF PARTICIPATION		External experts		Risk Trade-off Analysis and Deliberation Necessary
		Regulatory bodies, industry experts		Risk Balancing necessary
			Scientific Risk Assessment necessary	
	Use existing routines to assess risks	Maximise the scientific knowledge of the risk and mitigation options	Involve all affected stakeholders to collectively decide best way forward	Societal debate about the risk and its underlying implications
RISK MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES	Routine operations	Robustness focused	Resilience focused	Dialogue based
		Risk reduction	Precaution-based	
RISK CHARACTERISTIC	Simple	Complexity	Uncertainty	Ambiguity

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Adapted from: IRGC, 2005 and Klinke & Renn, 2002

Question:

Do you think citizens/societal groups trust scientific information on the release of nanoparticles if it is provided by industry? [yes/no]

What, if anything, should happen to enhance trust between industry and societal stakeholders? [open question]

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Knowledge characterization and risk evaluation

- Compare the outcome of risk and concern assessment
- Determine the significance and acceptability of the risk and to prepare decisions.
- Characterize the state of knowledge: characterize risk as simple, complex, uncertain or ambiguous, or (most often) a combination thereof.
- Make decision whether the risk is acceptable, tolerable or unacceptable.
- Decide option for management.

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Accepted/trusted knowledge and research?

Spontaneously mentioned criteria for knowledge and research:
 They must must be ...

Criteria	Number of times mentioned
... scientific	4 times
... validated / peer reviewed	4 times
... made public / published	2 times
... independent	4 times, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 time with the remark 'as long as it is validated' • 1 time with the question 'who pays?'
... repeated / evolving in time	2 times
... from renown / reputed institutes	2 times
... international (EU / global)	2 times

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- What sources are trusted?
 Mentioned are:
 - Research institutions
 - Universities
 - Medical institutes
 - Associations
 - Global bodies (like WHO)
- What sources are not trusted?
 - Wikipedia
 - Social media

Question:

Are you aware of concerns expressed by societal groups and/or citizens on the emission of nanomaterials from rubber tyres or products your company may be manufacturing? [Yes/no]

If so, could you briefly indicate what that concern was, and where we could find more information on it? [Open question]

Gov4Nano: Grant N°814401
NANORIGO: Grant N°814530
RiskGONE: Grant N°814425

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Thank you for your attention!

<https://nanorigo.eu/>

arto.saamanen@ttl.fi

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Gov4Nano: Grant N°814401
NANORIGO: Grant N°814530
RiskGONE: Grant N°814425

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Appendix 9.2

“Rubber granulate”, a case study for using the framework

Making sense of the 'rubber granulate' case with the NRGF

A case study for using the framework

 NANORIGO European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme grant agreement No 814530

Nanotechnology Risk Governance Framework

2006/2007: RIVM research on rubber granulate >> risk assessment-based advice

Based on various earlier studies, RIVM National Institute for Public Health and the Environment concluded that **it was unlikely that playing sports on synthetic turf fields with rubber granulate would have any health effects and that people playing sports could continue using rubber granulate fields.**

- In 2006, RIVM conducted a thorough study of the information available worldwide at that time about the possible health effects of exposure to rubber granulate.
- In 2007, RIVM performed air measurements above synthetic turf fields and published a report on the matter.
- RIVM works in an international network of experts and never bases any of its recommendations on a single study.
- etc

RIVM Committed to health and sustainability

Topics About RIVM International Publications

Home Rubber granulate Previous research into rubber granulate

Previous research into rubber granulate

In this topic

Publication date 12/14/2016 - 00:00 Modification date 01/17/2019 - 15:33

Current news

Environmental impact study on rubber granulate 2018

Research into rubber granulate on turf fields in 2016

Previous research into rubber granulate

RIVM advice in 2006

In 2006, RIVM concluded that risks could indeed be released in small quantities from rubber granulate in synthetic turf fields. Based on the available data there did not seem to be any grounds for concluding that these small quantities could lead to a health risk. The granulate also contains so-called plasticisers. No health risk had been described in connection with plasticisers in the event that granulate was swallowed. As regards the other chemical substances which may be found in rubber granulate, no data were available which could be used to estimate the health risk. Given that no health risk was associated with risks, which are the most hazardous component in rubber granulate, it seemed likely that the same would apply to other substances.

5 February 2021 - WP3 >> WP5

OECD best practices, 2015

Best Practices on Health and Environment Nanotechnology and Tyres: Elements for a Risk Assessment Framework

This publication is available electronically, at no charge.

For this and many other Environment, Health and Safety publications, consult the OECD's World Wide Web site (www.oecd.org/chemicalsafety/)

NANOTECHNOLOGY AND TYRES: ELEMENTS FOR A RISK ASSESSMENT

INTRODUCTION

This Risk Assessment Framework (RAF) for Nanotechnology and Tyres provides guidance to develop company-specific risk assessments and/or risk management strategies for using nanomaterials as additives in tyres.

Despite the focus on tyres and the use of nanomaterials, it is likely that this RAF may provide useful lessons for various types of manufacturing settings. It could also be applicable to other types of "difficult substances" which are less understood in terms of their potential hazards.

Objective:

The best practices outlined in this Risk Assessment Framework (RAF) aim to provide a method for evaluating the potential human health and environmental concerns associated with the entire life cycle of nanomaterials used in tyres, focusing on the tyre manufacturing process. The life cycle of tyres includes the manufacture of tyres, mounting tyres on vehicles, the use of tyres on vehicles and the end-of-life of tyres.

They aim to allow the user of a new nanomaterial to evaluate the associated risks and to make decisions for minimising those risks. This general methodology has been developed as guidance for stakeholders to proactively minimise potential concerns for any nanomaterial of interest that is under development.

The elements in this manual are extracted from the OECD report on **Nanotechnology and Tyres: Greening Industry and Transport (2015)**.

5 February 2021 - WP3 >> WP5

Risk assessment >> management

- Standard, conventional process

5 February 2021 - WP3 >> WP5

FRAMEWORK STEPS AND ILLUSTRATIVE EXAMPLES

The Risk Assessment Framework covers three steps:

- Phase I – Problem formulation and scoping;
- Phase II – Planning and conducting the risk assessment; and
- Phase III – Risk management.

Figure 2: The organisation and the flow of the RAF.

2016 : public opinion concerns in the NL (1)

- Health concerns >> new scientific technical assesement

Step 2.

5 February 2021 - WP3 >> WP5

RIVM Committed to health and sustainability

Home > Rubber granulate

Rubber granulate

Rubber granulate is used on synthetic turf fields to give them the properties of a natural grass field. It is made from rubber tyres.

In this topic

Publication date 11/07/2016 - 00:00 Modification date 01/17/2019 - 18:29

Current news

- Environmental impact study on rubber granulate 2018
- Research into rubber granulate on turf fields in 2016
- Previous research into rubber granulate

RIVM report: Evaluation of health risks of playing sports on synthetic turf pitches with rubber granulate

In March 2017 RIVM published a compilation of the initial 2016 report and all the scientific background documents: Evaluation of health risks of playing sports on synthetic turf pitches with rubber granulate. Scientific background document.

2016: public opinion concerns in the NL (2)

- Health concerns
 - >> dialogue with affected public and other citizens to understand concerns and address them

5 February 2021 - WP3 >> WP5

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Core functions

+ can integrate other

7

2018: environmental impacts?

5 February 2021 - WP3 >> WP5

RIVM Committed to health and sustainability

National Institute for Public Health and the Environment
Ministry of Health, Welfare and Sport

Home > News > Rubber granulate on synthetic turf fields causes environmental impact

Rubber granulate on synthetic turf fields causes environmental impact

Publication date 07/03/2018 - 00:00

Download (Dutch report, English synopsis)

- The environmental impact of rubber infill near synthetic turf fields

See also

- Environmental impact study on rubber granulate 2018

Use of rubber granulate sourced from car tyres, on **synthetic** turf fields can be harmful to the environment in the close vicinity of these fields. Substances leach from rubber granulate and enter the soil in the field border and in the ditches. Children at play and pets or cattle that occasionally ingest soil containing rubber granulate are not at risk. In order to protect the environment, RIVM recommends that measures be taken to prevent the spreading of rubber granulate to the field borders and to limit the emission of substances via the drainage water.

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"moving up to ECHA" > management decision > regulation

ECHA > News > Hot topics > Granules and mulches on sports pitches and playgrounds

Hot topics

- Preventing cancer
- Skin sensitising chemicals
- Perfluoroalkyl chemicals (PFAS)
- Lead in shot, bullets and fishing weights
- Microplastics
- Granules and mulches on sports pitches and playgrounds
- Tattoo inks and permanent make-up
- Glythoxale
- Endocrine disruptors
- Biopreserv A

Granules and mulches on sports pitches and playgrounds

For many years, sports players have used all-weather pitches for football, gaelic sports, rugby, lacrosse and other sports. These artificial playing surfaces often use **rubber granules** as infill to make the pitches more durable, weather-proof and to add shock absorption and traction.

Playground surfaces also often use loose **rubber mulches** underneath swings, slides and other playground equipment to cushion the ground when a child falls. The granules and mulches are often made from scrap end-of-life tyres (ELTs) that are broken up and ground down into smaller forms.

The granules and mulches may contain a number of potentially hazardous substances including polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), metals, and phthalates, and they may also release volatile organic hydrocarbons (VOCs) and semi-volatile organic hydrocarbons (SVOCs). The presence of these hazardous substances has led to concerns about the safety of artificial sports pitches and playgrounds.

- 1 What are the health risks to humans?
- 2 Further investigation to clarify uncertainties
- 3 Proposed restriction by the Netherlands
- 4 Committee opinions
- 5 European Commission decision
- 6 Is that it?

FURTHER INFORMATION

- ECHA
 - ECHA's scientific committees support restricting PAHs in granules and mulches (Press release, 18 September 2016)
 - Lower concentration limit proposed for PAHs found in granules and mulches (Press release, 18 August 2016)
 - Restriction proposal
 - Recycled rubber infill causes a very low level of concern (Press release, 19 February 2017)
 - ECHA's evaluation on whether recycled rubber filling on artificial sports grounds poses a health risk (Open SC report, 28 February 2017) (PDF)
 - Assessment to the 2017 report (PDF)
 - Call for evidence on the use of recycled rubber granules used as infill material in synthetic turf (PDF)
- ECHA evaluating whether recycled rubber filling on artificial sports grounds poses a health risk (Open SC report, 28 February 2017)
- Artificial pitches – safe, not perfect (ECHA Newsletter – May 2017)
- European Commission
 - European Commission's request for ECHA to assess health risks of recycled rubber granules (1 June 2016)

Step 4.

Step 5.

Planned timetable for restriction proposal on PAHs in granules and mulches used as infill

Future timetables are tentative

Activity	Timeline
Intention to prepare restriction dossier	30 June 2017
Call for evidence	23 July – 18 October 2017
Workshop hosted by RWM	24 November 2017
Submission of restriction dossier	20 July 2018
Public consultation of the Annex XV dossier	19 September 2018 – 19 March 2019
RAC opinion	7 June 2019
Draft SEAC opinion	14 June 2019
Public consultation on draft SEAC opinion	19 June 2019 – 19 August 2019
Combined final opinion submitted to the Commission	October 2019
Draft amendment to the Annex XVII (draft restriction) by Commission	Within 3 months of receipt of opinion
Discussions with Member State authorities and vote	2019-2020
Scrutiny by Council and European Parliament	Before adoption (3 months)
Restriction adopted (if agreed)	2020

5 February 2021 – WPS >> WPS

There exists already many 'frameworks' and tools, primarily for risk and safety assessment of nanotechnology

Environment International 95 (2016) 36-53

Contents lists available at ScienceDirect

Environment International

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/envint

Review article

Frameworks and tools for risk assessment of manufactured nanomaterials

Nano Today (2014) 9, 546-549

Available online at www.sciencedirect.com

ScienceDirect

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/nano

NEWS AND OPINIONS

A unified framework for nanosafety is needed

Janeck J. Scott-Fordsmand^{a,*,} S. Pozzi-Mucelli^{b,} L. Tre K. Aschberger^{c,} S. Sabella^{a,} U. Vogel^{c,} C. Poland^{d,} D. B. T. Fernandes^{e,} S. Gottardo^{f,} S. Hankin^{g,} M. G. J. Hartl^{h,} N. B. Hartmann^{h,} D. Hristozov^{g,} K. Hund-Rinke^{h,} H. Johnston^{g,} A. Marcomini^{h,} O. Panzer^{i,} D. Roncato^{j,} A. T. Saber^{k,} H. Wallin^{l,} V. Stone^g

nature nanotechnology

ARTICLES

https://doi.org/10.1038/441565-018-0120-4

A framework for sustainable nanomaterial selection and design based on performance, hazard, and economic considerations

Mark M. Falinski^{1,2} and Julie B. Zimmerman^{1,2}

Engineered nanomaterials conventional materials

GoNano

calIBRAte nano risk governance

Home Events Nano-Risk Governance Portal Nano-Safety Cluster Week Partners Results Res

News / Get involved: Test risk governance models

Are you involved in activities concerning R&D, production, marketing, use, risk assessment and management, inspection, insurance, calIBRAte invites you to get involved in the project and test one of the models identified as potentially suitable:

- NanoSector Control Banding
- GASENano
- LICARNA nanoscan
- BIALIA SprayScan 2.3
- Stoffmanager Nano
- ANSES: CB Nanosorb
- Control Banding nanosoft
- Precautionary Matrix
- ISO 15189:2013
- ConsEpo Nano
- SingleEpo Nano (SEBN)
- SEVEN

The calIBRAte framework will link different nano-specific models and methods into a system-of-systems (SoS), which compare assessment, prioritisation and management of occupational, consumer and environmental risks associated with production and models will be aligned to support decisions along the research and innovation value chain, from basic research to market launch

5 February 2021 – WPS

(Abstract) **several risk governance frameworks have been developed.** In our study, we present and review those, and identify a set of **criteria and tools for risk evaluation, mitigation, and communication, the implementation of which can inform better risk management decision-making by various stakeholders from e.g., industry, regulators, and the civil society.**

... specific methods from decision science and information technologies that can improve the existing risk governance tools so that they can communicate, evaluate, and mitigate risks more transparently, taking stakeholder perspectives and expert opinion into account, and considering all relevant criteria in establishing the risk-benefit balance of these emerging technologies to enable more robust decisions about the governance of their risks....

Risk governance

Governance refers to the actions, processes, traditions and institutions by which authority is exercised and decisions are taken and implemented.

Involves **multi-disciplinary** sciences and **multi-stakeholder** approaches

A **FRAMEWORK** for risk governance is based on a defined and structured **process** to addressing **risk** in a comprehensive and holistic manner. This includes:

- Identification, incl. **early-warning** systems/signals
- Assessment (hazard, exposure, vulnerability), incl. **models and tools**
- Evaluation of acceptability, incl. people's **perception and concern**, through **stakeholder involvement**
- Decision-making (incl. **MCDA**...)
- Management (incl. **regulation**)
- **Communication** of risk and feedback

References for the case

- Rivm
 - <https://www.rivm.nl/en/rubber-granulate>
 - <https://www.rivm.nl/en/news/rubber-granulate-on-synthetic-turf-fields-causes-environmental-impact>
 - Synthetic turf pitches with rubber granulate infill: are there health risks for people playing sports on such pitches? May 2020 Journal of Exposure Science & Environmental Epidemiology 30(3) DOI: 10.1038/s41370-018-0106-1
 - Public perception of contentious risk
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6616659/>
- Echa <https://echa.europa.eu/hot-topics/granules-mulches-on-pitches-playgrounds>

Appendix 9.3

Illustrating and applying the NANORIGO framework with Smart Nanomaterials

Illustrating and applying the NRGF with Smart Nanomaterials (SNM)

Contents

Introduction to the case 1

 Benefits and opportunities..... 2

 Challenges 2

Applying the NANORIGO Nanotechnology Risk Governance Framework (NRGF) 3

 Stakeholders’ views..... 4

Conclusion 5

This case presents a summary application of the NRGF to the case of smart nanomaterials (SMN). The case was discussed at an internal workshop of the NANORIGO consortium on 21 April 2021. Separately, a slide presentation is available for use in a role play among stakeholders.

Introduction to the case

Smart nanomaterials (SNM) present specific challenges regarding their assessment (safety, risk, impact, sustainability).

We anticipate that it will be particularly difficult to design SNM that are ‘safe and sustainable by design’, as expected in the EU Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability.

‘Smart nanomaterials’ are defined as "advanced nanomaterials that actively respond to external stimuli". Also called active, adaptive, or

Figure 1 - creating a general purpose technology in three stages between 2000 and 2030. Original in Roco, M.C., Mirkin, C., and Hersam, M.C. (2011) Nanotechnology research directions for societal needs in 2020. *Journal of Nanoparticle Research*, 13(3), 897–919

stimuli-responsive materials, they are materials that timely and reversibly change certain critical properties during use. ¹

In 2019 ECHA, identified 48 nano-enabled products in the 2nd generation (materials and structures) and 8 in the 3rd generation (systems), with about 70% of them already on the market.² The majority are for medical applications, about a quarter are for electronics.

Benefits and opportunities

There are many expected opportunities for smart nanomaterials (SNM) in medicine, cosmetics, food, food packaging, electronic applications, environmental applications (gas detection, contamination remediation), or agriculture. Novel or enhanced properties improve performance over conventional products and processes. For example, used in sensors or targeted delivery systems, specific functions are activated upon exposure to one or more external stimuli.

Challenges

However, due to their changing properties, SNM pose crucial challenges to risk assessors who cannot predict with sufficient certainty the behaviour of the materials and their possible toxicological effects after release into the environment and during the whole life cycle. The use of smart nanomaterials in industry is promising, but there are concerns that "smart nanomaterials and enabled products may present new challenges for safety and sustainability assessment due to their complexity and dynamic behaviour" (Gottardo et al., 2021) Depending on the domain of application, risk assessment is often insufficient on regulatory requirements for safety, and on expectations on long-term environmental sustainability. Questions, gaps, research priorities include:

- Are there risks that current tools for risk assessment are ill-designed to identify and assess?
- What kind of tools is needed to assess the safety and long-term environmental sustainability of smart nanomaterials?
- Would a precautionary approach be advised for smart nanomaterials? How to balance innovation and precaution in view of environmental sustainability³?
- Are existing regulatory framework appropriate?

¹ see for example:

- Mihail Roco defines 3 stages of NT, each of which include two generations of NT products.
 - Mihail Roco, Progress in Governance of Converging Technologies Integrated from the Nanoscale (2007) <https://nyaspubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1196/annals.1382.002>
 - Mihail Roco, Building Foundational Knowledge and Infrastructure for Nanotechnology: 2000–2030. August 2016 ACS Symposium Series DOI:10.1021/bk-2016-1220.ch004. In book: Nanotechnology: Delivering on the Promise Volume 1 (pp.39-52). <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1002/9781119371762.ch1>
- IRGC, International Risk Governance Council. *Nanotechnology risk governance white paper*, 2006, and [policy brief](#), 2007
- **ECHA A state of play study of the market for so called" next generation" nanomaterials (2019) DOI: 10.2823/242422**
- Towards safe and sustainable innovation in nanotechnology: State-of-play for smart nanomaterials. Stefania Gottardo, Agnieszka Mech, Jana Drbohlavova, Aleksandra Małyska, Søren Bøwadt, Juan Riego Sintes, Hubert Rauscher *NanoImpact* 21 (2021) 100297 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.impact.2021.100297>

² ECHA A state of play study of the market for so called" next generation" nanomaterials (2019) DOI: 10.2823/242422

³ André Gatzò, case study for the RECIPES project <https://recipes-project.eu/results/case-study-5-nanotechnologies>

Applying the NANORIGO Nanotechnology Risk Governance Framework (NRGF)

1. PREASSESSMENT – SETTING THE SCENE

- The European Green Deal, EC action plan for a Circular Economy, new EU Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability (CSS) require that any new material or product should be safe *and sustainable*
- Product marketing by industry requires: compliance with regulation AND acceptability by consumers
- SNM and enabled products may present new challenges for safety and sustainability assessment due to their complexity and dynamic behaviour
- Existing regulatory frameworks are *to some extent* ill-prepared to address them
- Need to consider safety and sustainability very early in the design stage
- This issue concerns scientists, technology developers, product manufacturers, regulators,

2. TECHNICAL RISK ASSESSMENT

- Despite the many scientific advancements in understanding the environmental and toxicological behaviour of nanomaterials, some open questions remain concerning the safety and sustainability of NM and become even more challenging when addressing new generations of NMs.
- Concerns regarding SNM that actively respond to external stimuli: crucial challenges in assessing and predicting the behaviour of SNM, and their possible toxicological effects after release into the environment, and during their whole lifecycle.
- Techniques, tools and instruments for risk assessment
 - What techniques are available to assess **safety** of a SNM focusing on the specific property of actively responding to external stimuli? Are these techniques mature? effective? What level of confidence do we have that they can provide a robust assessment?
 - More specifically, are there techniques to assess 'safety-by-design" (ie. material is non hazardous for humans and the environment; production eliminates risks at the workplace; waste should be avoided during the entire life cycle exposure to the SNM, through efficient recycling and disposal)
 - Also, are there techniques for **Life Cycle Analyiss**?
 - and finally, are there techniques to assess **sustainability** of a SNM? For example: LICARA NanoSCAN, to evaluate environmental, economic and social benefits against risks of SNM compared to conventional NM with similar function
- Outcome of technical risk assessment:
 - What results have been obtained so far? are they reproducible? can regulators rely on them?
- Characterisation of the gaps and deficits in knowledge and tools to establish knowledge, esp. regarding release into the environment and exposure

3. CONCERN ASSESSMENT

- Regarding safety and sustainability and the need to take into account people's opinions, concerns, expectation, social preferences, the purpose of the concern assessment is to analyse consumers and the public's acceptance of various SNM. the goal of both industry and regulators will be to ensure that consumer accept the SNM-enabled products that are authorised for market application and products.
- at a broader level and given the innovative and dynamic capacity of chemical technologies and industry, a broader objective is to build social trust in the industrial innovation process, while recognizing that risk may develop and will be addressed and managed in an appropriate manner. Risk governance is expected to ensure that the needs of all actors, including society,

will be met, and their concerns addressed. An inclusive system must be created for effective concern assessment, which involves a broad range of stakeholders in the research, design, development, production, consumption & recycling process.

4. EVALUATION

- Risk assessment must provide an outcome that enables industry and regulators to take their decision: seek authorisation (or not), authorise (or not), produce for the market (or not), etc. Regarding SNM and in the context of the CSS, the following aspects may be particularly challenging for decision-makers whether in industry or regulation:
 - How to assess the safety of an active product?
 - Is safety-by-design SaDB applicable to SNM? this can only be answered after SaBD has been clearly defined for regulatory purposes. NANoREG defines SaBD as "a process enabling an early stage application of the precautionary principle by means of considering health and environmental safety in addition to function in the design phase of a material. Other definitions must be considered as well
 - Is it possible to make a consensus evaluation on the risk?
 - Decisions about risk often require resolving risk-benefit trade-offs. Are trade-offs clearly identified? how can they be resolved?
 - Many SNM are in development phase, will result from an emerging technology, and present known risk as well as emerging or potential risk. Industry and regulators will thus be confronted to policy trade-offs related to well-known conflicts between precaution and innovation.
 - On sustainability: the score of advanced materials depends on the extent to which the individual components of the score, i.e. economy, environment and society, are valued by an assessor, and which sub criteria contribute most to an improvement in a product's sustainability. Criteria proposed by JRC for sustainability-by-design (SubD) include....
 - Are product liability issues more complicated with SNM than non-active NM?
- Eventually, can industry manage the known or potential risk, so that the residual risks are tolerable? Can regulators require the use of certain instruments for risk assessment and management that will provide sufficient confidence that the risks will be controlled or contained?
- Is the regulatory framework adapted?

5. RISK MANAGEMENT

- Overall, a robust but flexible regulatory framework to address the new challenges of SNM is probably what would be needed. The framework should be flexible to keep pace with innovation without creating unnecessary barriers for industry. Relevant aspects to consider include:
 - Standards, certification
 - Safe Innovation Approach (SIA) combines Safe-by-design in industry settings and Regulatory Preparedness by regulators
- Planned Adaptive Regulation. Analogy with EMA's 'adaptive pathways' (also used by US FDA in 'fast-track-approval'). Analogy in AI-based medical devices in EU and the US.

Stakeholders' views

In April 2021, NANORIGO organised an internal exercise to understand the role of 3 stakeholder groups with regards to their needs and expectations for effective risk governance of SNMs. In summary, the views were that:

- For regulators, whose goal is to *ensure safety and sustainability of nanomaterials, before they are placed on the market, without constraining innovation*:
SNM introduce new components to any cost-benefit analysis (CBA). CBA is not neutral, it is a political concept/tool. One of the recurring question is how to drive or orientate a EU way of doing things (including balancing the precautionary principle and innovation)? CBAs attach different weighting to different factors, which results from a policy or governance decision. This kind of issue requests involving views from other stakeholders than the major ones. Many regulators don't have much experience in 'needs assessments' and CBAs. A joint application of the NRGF could help develop a common ground.
- For industry, whose goal is to: *develop and produce nanomaterials, and place them on the market. Safety and sustainability matter but innovation drives economic competitiveness*:
In the face of opportunities and challenges of SNMs, industry would welcome recommendations on how to act in a responsible manner – ensuring safe and sustainable development, but this needs to be balanced against the risk of inhibiting innovation. Industry responds to societal demands with innovation. Applying the NRGF could provide support in understanding sustainability aspects with full LCA. Safety important, and complex for longer-term effects.
- For NGOs, whose goal is to *act to represent the interest of the general public, and exercise their power through expertise, awareness raising, advocacy activities and public activism, for instance to influence policy contents and its adequate implementation*:
Smart nanomaterials require 'smart' risk assessment: new assessment methodologies to assess new risks. In case of uncertainty, precautionary principle should be applied ('no data, no application'). Using the NRGF could facilitate a discussion about why these materials are needed and cost-benefit analysis (Benefits for whom? cost for whom?)
- in summary, the three stakeholder groups noted the following three issue:
 - cost-benefit analyses should be central in the risk assessment of SNM,
 - those who evaluate outcome of risk assessment in view of management decisions would be advised to consider both short and long term effects, and
 - appropriate and careful balancing of interests and views seems necessary, considering the many uncertainties and ambiguities involved.

Conclusion

A framework for risk governance can help by providing a structured process to

- elaborate safety and risk assessment and management
- evaluate and decide of what is an 'acceptable' level of risk
- address tensions between precaution and innovation
- develop principles and guidelines for addressing long-term sustainability risk
- plan adaptability in regulatory frameworks
- address a range of issues related to emerging technologies
- co-creation by stakeholders
- work towards the future

but although this can be done in a distributed manner by each actor in the chain, from research and development to regulation, production and distribution, it can be more more effective if there is some form of coordination or dialogue among risk assessors and then risk managers in regulation and in industry.

Appendix 9.4

Slides for role play “Applying the NANORIGO framework with Smart Nanomaterials”

NANORIGO

21 April 2021 annual meeting

Role play on smart nanomaterials (NRGFramework and NRGCouncil)

13.04.2021 - WP4 NRG

1

Role play – briefing to players

The objective of the role play is to test a **process** of how the Council can serve to facilitate the development of a common view concerning how risks can be assessed and how applications can be regulated

- *The assembly of members of the NRG has determined that the use of **smart nanomaterials** in industry is promising, but there are concerns that "smart nanomaterials and enabled products may present new challenges for safety and sustainability assessment due to their complexity and dynamic behaviour" (Gottardo et al., 2021)*
- *It requests the NRG management committee to convene the 3 stakeholder groups to come with their respective positions, and then discuss how to develop an '**informed opinion**' (advice) that will be brought to the attention of EU regulators and EU industry associations.*

Briefing information about 'smart nanomaterials'

- 'Smart nanomaterials' are defined as "advanced nanomaterials that actively respond to external stimuli"
- **Please read before the role play:**
Towards safe and sustainable innovation in nanotechnology: State-of-play for smart nanomaterials. Stefania Gottardo, Agnieszka Mech, Jana Drbohlavova, Aleksandra Matyska, Søren Bøwadt, Juan Riego Sintes, Hubert Rauscher NanoImpact 21 (2021) 100297 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.impact.2021.100297>
- *Optional material* - Literature on governance of "next generation" nanomaterials" in the sense of emerging technology, such as:
 - ECHA, A state of play study of the market for so called" next generation" nanomaterials (2019) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.impact.2021.100297>
 - Mihail Roco, Progress in Governance of Converging Technologies Integrated from the Nanoscale (2007) <https://nyaspubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1196/annals.1382.002>

Smart nanomaterials

- Expected **opportunities** (promises of net benefits) in medicine, cosmetics, food, food packaging, electronic applications, environmental applications (gas detection, contamination remediation), agriculture >> innovation
- Sensors, targeted delivery systems >> SNM timely and reversibly **change certain critical properties during use**, and activates specific functions upon exposure to one or more external stimuli
- **ECHA** (2019) identified 48 applications in the 2nd generation (materials and structures) and 3rd generation of NT (systems)
- **Challenges** (do we have the tools and data?) for safety assessment, risks assessment, safety-by-design, LCA and sustainability-by-design (EU green deal, EC action plan for a circular economy, EU chemicals strategy for sustainability)
- **Problem** of applicability of definitions, risk assessment tools and regulation (eg. REACH may not fully cover the specific features of SNM)
- What are the **views** (opinions, concerns, preferences...) of affected people?
- This issue concerns every one in the NM value chain: scientists, technology developers, product manufacturers, regulators,...

Background information about the NRGC

Participants in the role play are expected to be familiar with:

- The NRG Council, as in
 - NMBP-13 proposal. Cf. 'mindmaps' will be presented on 12 April
 - Nanorigo D4.4
- The NRG Framework (as in D3.2a/b)

Organisation of the role play

- Participants are pre-assigned to a stakeholder group (regulators, industry, NGOs/&CSOs) and are expected to **participate as representatives of the group** in which they are. Researchers are not a specific stakeholder group. In this exercise, they are invited to 'think as' the stakeholder group they represent
- The main objective is to test the **process** of how the Council can serve to facilitate the development of a common view (**'informed opinion'**) **concerning how risks can be assessed and how applications can be regulated.**
- To prepare the 'informed opinion', each group will reply to a few questions asked in two rounds of discussion.
- Producing shared knowledge / content is not the main goal of the role play. Nevertheless, participants are expected to work towards producing one 'informed opinion'

Group 1: regulators

Facilitators: Martin Mullins, Marie-Valentine Florin

Goal of regulators is to ensure safety and sustainability of nanomaterials, before they are placed on the market, without constraining innovation.

- Assessment of risks from SNM
 - What do you know and don't know?
 - What do you need to know, how?
- Management of risks from SNM
 - Are the tools, existing procedures applicable?
 - Suggestions for regulation
- Communication
 - What would you say about risks and benefits from smart nanomaterials?
- About the NRGCC:
 - How would the presence/availability of RGC impact on regulatory processes
 - Would you use the RGC as

13.04.2021 - WP4 NRGCC

Group 2: industry

Facilitators: Mark Morrison, Nils Bohmer

Goal of industry is to develop and produce nanomaterials, and place them on the market. Safety and sustainability matter but innovation drives economic competitiveness.

- Assessment of risks from SNM
 - What do you know and don't know?
 - What do you need to know, how?
- Management of risks from SNM
 - Are the tools, existing procedures applicable?
 - Suggestions for regulation
- Communication
 - What would you say about risks and benefits from smart nanomaterials?

Group 3: NGOs / CSOs

Facilitators: Christina Benighaus, Daan Schuurbiens

Goal of NGOs/CSOs is to act to represent the interest of the general public, and exercise their power through expertise, awareness raising, advocacy activities and public activism, for instance to influence policy contents and its adequate implementation

- Assessment of risks from SNM:
 - What do you know and don't know?
 - What do you need to know, how?
- Management of risks from SNM:
 - Are the tools, existing procedures applicable?
 - Suggestions for regulation
- Communication
 - What would you say about risks and benefits from smart nanomaterials?

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Example of applications to discuss, for the purpose of developing your 'informed opinion'

• SMN in cosmetics

"recently a new family of stimuli-responsive nanocapsules designed to enclose a cosmetic ingredient able to treat different skin conditions (e.g. contact dermatitis, skin photo-damage) has been developed and commercialised (<https://www.emissarycosmetics.com/>). The PeptiCaps nanocapsules release the active ingredient in the desired location in response to changes of pH or presence of specific enzymes caused by the skin condition to be treated. Likewise, nanoencapsulates are used in some of the so called 'deodorants on request' to release a fragrance or a bacteria growth inhibitor in response to the changed pH, temperature or moisture of the skin".

• SMN in food packaging

"Stimuli responsive food packaging reacts to stimuli in the food or the environment to enable real time food quality and food safety monitoring or remediation. The most popular use of stimuli responsive nanomaterials in food packaging is the monitoring of gaseous compounds like O₂, CO₂ or ethylene present in the headspace of the package. responsive packaging will have a tremendous impact on food industry by reducing spoilage, food waste, food recalls, or foodborne illness outbreaks thus contributing to sustainable development and safety."

- Do we have the tools to assess the risks?
- Are the potential risks worth taking, in view of potential benefits elsewhere?
- What process do you recommend for considering possible revisions to the cosmetic product regulation / food packaging regulation

Organisation of the role play

1. 15' introduction: overview of the material provided, formation of the 3 groups
2. Round 1:
 - 30' work in group on the questions of the previous slide. Production of one summary slide
 - 20' Groups reconvene in plenary and briefly present their positions (slide)
 - Discussion:
 - Is there common ground? Common views on what we know and need to know about smart nanomaterials, and how to assess, regulate and communicate?
 - Main areas of agreement, variation, disagreement?
3. Round 2
 - 15' Back in breakout groups
 - How to take into account others' positions to come to an 'informed opinion' that satisfies all parties. Revision of the slide
 - or: What did you observe in the discussion in round 1 that should be taken into account in the design of the Council?
 - 15' Groups reconvene in plenary, and briefly report on their revised slide
 - Discussion:
 - Elements to include in an 'informed opinion' that would be presented to regulators
4. 20' Conclusions
 - Through this example, what have we seen are the most critical challenges that the Council could work to overcome, by pursuing the **goal** of.... (cf proposed goals that the Council will pursue)
 - What are the most obvious **activities** and services it could provide, and those that it should not provide? (cf. proposed activities & services)
 - Recommendations in terms of organisational structure?

Results and conclusion of the role play

Including discussion on the Council

Group 1: Regulators

Development of an **'informed opinion'** that will be brought to the attention of EU regulators and EU industry associations

Goal of regulators is to: ensure safety and sustainability of nanomaterials, before they are placed on the market, without constraining innovation.

- Interagency task needed for SNM

- Resource for medicines, cosmetics, environment...?
- Fits with EU approach to one substance-one assessment, focus on sustainability
- covered by current regulation??

1. Assessment of risks from SNM

- What we know and don't know:
 - As regulators, we are concerned by an enormous nr of issues that go wrong. Can we, regulators, deal with all the problems?
 - The field is moving really fast. Pacing problem. How can we, regulatory, develop a kind of 'radar' that helps us cope with these new development that are coming very fast.
 - LCAs. We need to ask for more information
 - There is already existing information that can be used to inform the assessment. But we need more
 - Cost-benefit analysis indicates lots of upsides, which requires a different type of expertise than the one regulators usually have. The NRG could help there
 - What we need to know, and how:
 - Emergent properties- does it change the toxicology assessment

2. Management of risks from SNM

- Are the existing tools and procedures applicable and sufficient?
 - Yes?
 - Pb of applicable legal definition and harmonization. Some NM may be exempt from REACH? Focus on substance does not suffice
 - regulators may: ensure safety or create a framework for this
 - There are lots of tools available and useful but they are not mandatory for the dossiers. Question of scalability. Some of them should be mandated.
 - So far, regulation has not focused on long-term impacts (& chronic impact). For SNM we need to address this
 - Mandate of regulators may have to be amended? How to take into account innovation?

3. Communication

- What would you say about risks and benefits from smart nanomaterials?
- Regulators are not so much involved in communicating about benefits
- Alternatives. What is the risk of not using a particular SMN?

4. About the NRG

- How would the presence/availability of RGC impact on regulatory processes - for example could it potentially strengthen your hand as an entity - if societal concern is reflected in RGC outputs? Would you use the RGC as resource?
- How would the NRG 'change the world' here? How would it improve the life of regulators? The NRG cannot 'step over' my mandate. NRG is an advisory body that can trigger the regulatory process.
 - Cost-benefit analysis
 - How does this influence the way the NRG operate?
 - CBA differs to some extent between the US and the EU, but seems to be moving closer
 - Innovation, competitiveness

Our **'informed opinion'**:

SNM introduce new components to any CBA. CBA is not neutral, it is a political concept/tool. Do we consider the NRG to drive its orientation from a EU way of doing things (including balancing the PP and innovation). CBA attach different weighting to different factors, which is a governance issue. This kind of issue requests involving view from other stakeholders than the major ones. Many regulators don't have much experience in 'needs assessments' and CBAs. The NRG could help develop a common ground (with the RGF)

Group 2: Industry

Development of an **'informed opinion'** that will be brought to the attention of EU regulators and EU industry associations

Goal of industry is to develop and produce nanomaterials, and place them on the market. Safety and sustainability matter but innovation drives economic competitiveness.

1. Assessment of risks from SNM

- What we know and don't know:
 - Early notification of any issues based on scientific knowledge
 - Own procedures to monitor risks, but wary of over-restrictive regulations
 - What differentiates the 'new' material from what exists already
 - Not a completely new field- already risk mgt procedures in place for smart materials that are already being used
 - Support knowledge transfer within companies and knowledge from Council into companies (Council should be a repository of knowledge)
- What we need to know, and how:
 - Risk-benefit relationship - although this can be difficult early on in the innovation process
 - Sustainability should perhaps come before safety in this cycle
 - Differences between different types of industry
 - Smart nanomaterials change through whole life-cycle (this means in terms of changing in response to stimuli and eventual disposal/reuse)

2. Management of risks from SNM

- Are the existing tools and procedures applicable and sufficient?
 - Unlikely to be available
 - Most (large) industry would act responsibly - go beyond future regulatory requirements
 - Needs transparency
 - Need to understand the new functionality in the context of existing risk mgt

Suggestions for regulation:

- Expect mutual trust in this - safe environment for data sharing
- Balance innovation vs regulation burden

3. Communication

- What would you say about risks and benefits from smart nanomaterials?
 - All concerned stakeholders need to be involved at earliest stage - improves transparency
 - Great potential, higher than risk and how this relates to other risks
 - Sector specific risks

4. Other information?

- Overall, industry would act in a responsible manner - ensuring safe and responsible development, but needs to be balanced against inhibiting innovation
- Industry responds to societal demands with innovation
- Council should provide support in understanding sustainable (full LCA) aspects first, safety important but more complex for longer-term effects

Group 3: NGOs/CSOs

Goal of NGOs/CSOs is to act to represent the interest of the general public, and exercise their power through expertise, awareness raising, advocacy activities and public activism, for instance to influence policy contents and its adequate implementation.

1. Assessment of risks from SNM

- What we know and don't know:
- **Smart nanomaterials require smart risk assessment: new assessment methodologies to assess new risks**
- In case of uncertainty, precautionary principle should be applied ('no data, no application')
- We already struggle managing the first generation, let alone next generations...
- Long-term vision: also include what is not known yet

- What we need to know, and how:
- **Do we need these materials?** Do the benefits outweigh the risks? NGOs don't necessarily see the use of smart nanomaterials in food packaging as progress (quite the opposite...). Should we not focus on something else? (Alternative technologies)
 - Same as with nanosilver socks: doesn't it create more problems than it solves?
 - Are there less toxic options?
 - Is a **subjective** question: many different views on this? Council itself cannot handle that question.
- What is the scope of risk analysis – consumer health, or ecosystem health? 'Benefits' vary depending on the scope! This shapes the risk assessment – and the jurisdictional consequences
 - What happens to materials after the product lifecycle (in effluent / environment)?
- We need **support** to get reliable information

2. Management of risks from SNM

- Are the existing tools and procedures applicable and sufficient?
- **What are the governance procedures within the Council? Who gets to say what, when?**
- **Who gets to shape the risk discussion? What is 'in' – and what is 'out'?**
- do we review the risk assessment PRIOR to use in the market (pre-registration) OR once it is in the marketplace?

- Suggestions for regulation:
 - Transition to sustainable system – from global make-take-waste to locally sourced values chains!
 - Create labels to ensure that products are safe

3. Communication

- What would you say about risks and benefits from smart nanomaterials?
- How is the outcome communicated? (100 pages of scientific text / a leaflet?)

4. Other information?

- **REPRESENTATION:**
 - NGOs are very diverse: from environmental / consumer / health organisations to industry associations (like NIA).

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Notes from 1st round reporting

Regulators

Ensuring safety

Industry

Developing products. Companies have management procedures in place but need to balance risks and innovation

Concerns about data sharing

Communication, transparency and reputational risks.

NGOs

SNMs require smart risk assessment – new products >> new methodologies

Do we really need these materials? Do benefits outweigh the risks, looking at long-term and systemic effects?

What will the mandate of the council be?

NGOs is not a unified group

Common themes:

Cost-benefit analysis central

Short term and long term

Balancing interests and views

Do you think that regulators will hinder innovation?

Do you think that industry will try to underestimate long term impacts that are not yet visible?

- **Regulators:**
SNMs introduce new components to any CBA. CBA is not neutral, it is a political concept/tool. Do we consider the NRGC to drive its orientation from a EU way of doing things (including balancing the PP and innovation)
- **Industry:**
Overall, industry would act in a responsible manner – ensuring safe and responsible development, but needs to be balanced against inhibiting innovation. Industry responds to societal demands with innovation. Council should provide support in understanding sustainable (full LCA) aspects first, safety important but more complex for longer-term effects
- **NGOS:**
 - Smart nanomaterials require smart risk assessment: new assessment methodologies to assess new risks. In case of uncertainty, precautionary principle should be applied ('no data, no application')
 - Do we need these materials? Cost-benefit-analysis: what are the methodologies (incl. criteria / procedures / conditions?) Benefits for whom?

Appendix 9.5

Trainer survey form

This poll evaluates whether the NANORIGO nanorisk governance framework improves training towards safe working practices and risk governance.

Section A: General questions

- A1. Training in the context of nanosafety research: From your point of view, what are the most important teaching goals in regard to a risk governance training for young scientists?**

- A2. Training in the context of nanosafety research: From your point of view, what are the most important elements of a risk governance framework?**

Easy to access internet landing page

User friendly guidance through the framework

Data collections

Tool collections

Communication platform

Risk governance process description

E-learning content

Risk governance council

Experts network

Section B: Pre-assessment phase: Define the issue, frame boundaries, identify existing conventions

Learning targets and teaching content:

The purpose of the pre-assessment is to frame the risk, to place an early warning, and to prepare for handling the risk. Pre-assessment involves relevant actors and identifies potential stakeholder groups for subsequent inclusion. It has to capture the various perspectives on the potential risk (simple, complex, uncertain, ambiguous), but also its opportunities, and strategies for addressing it.

Pre-assessment is setting the stage in the governance process. Erroneous decisions at this point of framing are the most critical, because here the agenda for the subsequent steps is defined.

B1. How essential are these teaching goals for a comprehensive understanding of risk governance?

- very essential
- essential
- not essential
- don't know

B2. What is your most important teaching goal at this point?

B3. Pre-assessment: How well is the NRGF process / NANORIGO portal aligned with your teaching goal?

- very well aligned
- aligned
- not aligned
- don't know

B4. Pre-assessment: How supportive is the NRGF process / NANORIGO portal to prepare for your training session?

- | | very
supportiv
e | support
ive | not
supportiv
e | don't
know |
|---|--------------------------|--------------------------|--------------------------|--------------------------|
| Efficiency (less time consuming, more cost effective) | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Effectivity (complete, consistent, state of the art training) | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |

Section C: Technical, scientific assessment phase: Hazard, exposure & vulnerability; consequence assessment

Technical, scientific assessment phase: Human, environmental hazard assessment; occupational, environmental, consumer exposure & vulnerability; consequence assessment.

Teaching goals and content:

The purpose of this step is to perform an analytical and technical assessment and to collect existing information about NMs' hazards, exposure and vulnerability of affected populations. Probability of occurrence and extent of harm and severity of consequences must be assessed, through appropriate models for human and environmental risk assessment.

Risk assessment synthesizes the knowledge base for subsequent decisions, including what options are available for preventing, mitigating, adapting to or approving the risk. Information for risk assessment studies is provided by particular safety studies and agreed upon methods, but due to the complex nature of NMs, these may be finally insufficient for an unambiguous risk assessment outcome.

C1. How essential are these teaching goals for a comprehensive understanding of risk governance?

- very essential
- essential
- not essential
- don't know

C2. What is your most important teaching goal at this point?

C3. Technical, Scientific assessment: How well is the NRGF process / NANORIGO portal aligned with your teaching goal?

- very well aligned
- aligned
- not aligned
- don't know

C4. Technical, Scientific assessment: How supportive is the NRGF process / NANORIGO portal to prepare for your training session?

very supportive supportive not supportive don't know

Efficiency (less time consuming, more cost effective)

.....

very supportive supportive not supportive don't know

Effectivity (complete, consistent, state of the art training)

.....

Section D: Opinion & concern assessment phase: Capture opinions, perceptions & concerns of affected populations

Teaching goals and content:

Concern assessment has to identify the opinions, perceptions, and concerns of directly affected stakeholders but also the socio-economic impact and economic benefits or harm of indirectly affected populations. Uncertainty in the context of new technologies raises the bar for the acceptance of nanotechnology-based products, because human behavior and decision making is driven by bounded rationality.

This makes clear that inclusiveness – “being heard” and informed participation of relevant stakeholders is the key in this stage. Information is the key to align perception driven decisions with decisions based on the outcomes of a technical risk assessment.

D1. How essential are these teaching goals for a comprehensive understanding of risk governance?

very essential

essential

not essential

don't know

D2. What is your most important teaching goal at this point?

D3. Opinion & Concern Assessment: How well is the NRGF process / NANORIGO portal aligned with your teaching goal?

very well aligned

aligned

not aligned

don't know

D4. Opinion & Concern Assessment: How supportive is the NRGF process / NANORIGO portal to prepare for your training session?

very supportive supportive not supportive don't know

Efficiency (less time consuming, more cost effective)

.....

very
supportiv
e support
ive not
supportiv
e don't
know

Effectivity (complete, consistent, state of the art training)

.....

Section E: Evaluation phase: Characterization of the risk

Teaching goals and content:

Risk evaluation is a phase of reflectiveness and accountable judgement, reviewing and weighing the outcome of pre-assessment, technical risk and concern assessment with criteria accepted by science and society.

It collects and summarizes information of all 3 preceding steps and reflects it from a decision-making perspective.

The final target is to prepare a foundation and to propose a strategy for the risk management phase, which can be led either by the principles of precautionary, or being dominated by the strategy of risk acceptability, risk sharing and mitigation, hence enabling responsible innovation.

However, acceptance is frequently a matter of trade-offs between risks and benefits on a qualitative scale.

E1. How essential are these teaching goals for a comprehensive understanding of risk governance?

very essential

essential

not essential

don't know

E2. What is your most important teaching goal at this point?

E3. Evaluation: How well is the NRGF process / NANORIGO portal aligned with your teaching goals?

very well aligned

aligned

not aligned

don't know

E4. Evaluation: How supportive is the NRGF process / NANORIGO portal to prepare for your training session?

	very supportiv e	support ive	not supportiv e	don't know
Efficiency (less time consuming, more cost effective)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effectivity (complete, consistent, state of the art training)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Section F: Management phase: Treatment and regulation of the risk

Teaching goals and content:

Risk management is a process that addresses the treatment and regulation of a risk by development and implementation of the actions and remedies required to avoid, retain, reduce or transfer the risk.

For standard risks, standard management instruments are frequently available and have to be appropriately evaluated, selected and adopted. However, sometimes an accepted and harmonized approach is not available, thus the design and generation of new risk management options may be needed.

An implemented risk management strategy has to cover the whole risk life-cycle, thus is made-to-last.

F1. How essential are these teaching gloals for a comprehensive understanding of risk governance?

very essential	<input type="checkbox"/>
essential	<input type="checkbox"/>
not essential	<input type="checkbox"/>
don't know	<input type="checkbox"/>

F2. What is your most important teaching goal at this point?

F3. Management: How well is the NRGF process / NANORIGO portal aligned with your teaching goals?

very well aligned	<input type="checkbox"/>
aligned	<input type="checkbox"/>
not aligned	<input type="checkbox"/>
don't know	<input type="checkbox"/>

F4. Management: How supportive is the NRGF process / NANORIGO portal to prepare for your training session?

	very supportiv e	support ive	not supportiv e	don't know
Efficiency (less time consuming, more cost effective)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effectivity (complete, consistent, state of the art training)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Section G: Monitoring & feedback phase: Monitoring the performance, evaluating and providing feedback

Monitoring & feedback phase: Monitoring the performance, evaluating and providing feedback to assessors and managers.

Teaching goals and content:

Monitoring of risk, monitoring the implemented risk management strategy and measures is critical, in particular to keep up with an evolving technical and regulatory environment, changes in the societal perception and tolerance to risk or increasing uncertainty or ambiguity on emerging new evidence.

A flexible governance process allows the integration of new concerns and findings in a transparent, fair and fast manner, by regularly feedback to and collection of feedback from all participating stakeholders, using methods provided by the NRGF core functions for communication.

G1. How essential are these teaching goals for a comprehensive understanding of risk governance?

very essential	<input type="checkbox"/>
essential	<input type="checkbox"/>
not essential	<input type="checkbox"/>
don't know	<input type="checkbox"/>

G2. What is your most important teaching goal at this point?

G3. Monitoring and Feedback: How well is the NRGF process / NANORIGO portal aligned with your teaching goal?

very well aligned	<input type="checkbox"/>
aligned	<input type="checkbox"/>
not aligned	<input type="checkbox"/>
don't know	<input type="checkbox"/>

G4. Monitoring and Feedback: How supportive is the NRGF process / NANORIGO portal to prepare for your training session?

	very supportive	supportive	not supportive	don't know
Efficiency (less time consuming, more cost effective)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effectivity (complete, consistent, state of the art training)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Section H: Your experience

H1. What is your primary target audience for training activities?

- Young scientist
- Researcher
- Regulator
- Public representative
- Trainer
- Manufacturer
- Worker
- Insurer
- Other

Other

H2. For the preparation of nanosafety and nanorisk governance training: Which public resources do / would you use, if any?

H3. Do you know the NANORIGO Nanotechnology Risk Governance Framework portal?

I have already utilized it

I have heard about it

I don't

Our sincere thanks for your participation. We will keep you informed about the outcomes of this survey.

Appendix 9.6

NRGF Web-platform validation

NRGF Web-platform validation: user experience from T5.1 case study “Training”

Main goal of the document

The objective of this document is to collect the opinion of the users of the NRGF web-platform developed within T3.6, in relation to its technical aspects, user-friendliness, content, design, and navigation experience. This action is part of the first phase of validation of the Nanorigo web-platform first prototype, which is carried out through the WP5 case studies.

The typology of questions is differentiated in 5 blocks, in order to cover all technical aspects related to the platform. Questions regarding the content itself are also collected, which will serve to give feedback to the work developed in WP1 and WP2 on sources of information and data, and tools. (Please, not that at the moment, there is still some content under development, which has not yet been implemented).

Contextualization: description of contents (key elements) integrated into the NRGF web-platform

- Risk Governance tools and approaches (WP2)
- Sources of high-quality data and guidance (WP1)
- Strategic screening decision support system (T3.2)
- ESEE and economic aspects (T3.4)
- Risk communication platform (T3.5)

Instructions for access

The platform (currently in prototype phase) is hosted at: <http://nanorigo.europeanprojects.net>

The web-based platform contains external functions which allows access to different existing tool, content, references, and links that aim to cover the needs of different types of stakeholders in relation to the governance of risks derived from nanotechnology.

In order to access, it is necessary to register beforehand, entering username and password.

When registering, a mandatory field must be filled in referring to the type of stakeholder that is the user in question. In this way the platform will adapt the tools according to the user's needs.

Choose the agreement option that most accurately represents the quality of the application you are evaluating.

Section 1 – Information and contents

1. The content of the web-platform is correct, well written and relevant to the purpose of the NRGF according to my needs.
 - a. Strongly agree
 - b. Agree
 - c. Neither agree nor disagree
 - d. Disagree
 - e. Strongly disagree

2. The information within the web-platform is complete but concise.
 - a. Strongly agree
 - b. Agree
 - c. Neither agree nor disagree
 - d. Disagree
 - e. Strongly disagree

3. The visual explanation of concepts - colour scale - is logical and intuitive.
 - a. Strongly agree
 - b. Agree
 - c. Neither agree nor disagree
 - d. Disagree
 - e. Strongly disagree

4. The information within the web platform seems to come from a reliable source.
 - a. Strongly agree
 - b. Agree
 - c. Neither agree nor disagree
 - d. Disagree
 - e. Strongly disagree

5. Other comments about the information and the contents of the platform.

Comments

1. c: The content can be deemed correct and after some revisions will be well written; however, we miss a comprehensive introduction resource to the general principles of the risk governance process and its particularities in the field of nano. This is an important issue for training, where a trainer (expert) has to make trainees (non-experts) familiar with risk governance. The help function just refers to a technical manual.
2. c: to our understanding the web-platform is work-in-progress and there are still substantial parts missing.
3. b. beside text, there is not a lot of visual content.

Section 2 – Individual assessment of functions

6. Before answering the following questions, please indicate the workflow you followed (the setups you used and their order)

Answer

Our selections have been made under the assumption that we are a training organization (= trainer with moderate to medium expertise) using this platform to make trainees (non-experts) familiar with risk governance (but not with all the particularities of all tools).

We selected:

Hazard assessment both for Human and Environment

Exposure assessment, occupational, consumer and environmental exposure

Fate assessment

Risk assessment both Human and Environment

Risk management

Monitoring and feedback

Physical state: Dry material, Nanoproduct

ELSEA aspects

Life cycle analysis

I'm an expert

I'm only looking for free tools

7. PRE-ASSESSMENT

The questions posed by the platform allow me to define the issue and frame the boundaries correctly.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

8. TECHNICAL SCIENTIFIC ASSESSMENT

The distinction made between the different types of tools according to the field of study

(human or environmental hazard, consumer exposure and vulnerability, consequences assessment) is appropriate.

- a. Strongly agree
- b. Agree
- c. Neither agree nor disagree
- d. Disagree
- e. Strongly disagree

9. TECHNICAL SCIENTIFIC ASSESSMENT

In order to be able to better evaluate each step of the platform, please indicate in which fields you have indicated your interest in the pre-assessment.

- a. Human hazard assessment
- b. Environmental hazard assessment
- c. Occupational, consumer and environmental exposure assessment
- d. Human and environmental risk assessment
- e. Risk management
- f. Monitoring and feedback
- g. ELSEA
- h. Life Cycle Assessment

10. TECHNICAL SCIENTIFIC ASSESSMENT

The quality and quantity of the tools offered by the platform is adequate.

- a. Strongly agree
- b. Agree
- c. Neither agree nor disagree
- d. Disagree
- e. Strongly disagree

11. TECHNICAL SCIENTIFIC ASSESSMENT

The explanation given for each of the tools (illustrations) is adequate.

- a. Strongly agree
- b. Agree
- c. Neither agree nor disagree
- d. Disagree
- e. Strongly disagree

12. OPINION AND CONCERN ASSESSMENT

The quality and quantity of the tools offered by the platform's is adequate.

- a. Strongly agree
- b. Agree
- c. Neither agree nor disagree
- d. Disagree
- e. Strongly disagree

13. OPINION AND CONCERN ASSESSMENT

The explanation given for each of the tools (illustrations) is adequate.

- a. Strongly agree
- b. Agree
- c. Neither agree nor disagree
- d. Disagree
- e. Strongly disagree

14. EVALUATION

The quality and quantity of the tools offered by the platform's is adequate.

- a. Strongly agree
- b. Agree
- c. Neither agree nor disagree
- d. Disagree
- e. Strongly disagree

15. EVALUATION

The explanation given for each of the tools (illustrations) is adequate.

- a. Strongly agree
- b. Agree
- c. Neither agree nor disagree
- d. Disagree
- e. Strongly disagree

16. MANAGEMENT

The quality and quantity of the tools offered by the platform's is adequate.

- a. Strongly agree
- b. Agree
- c. Neither agree nor disagree
- d. Disagree
- e. Strongly disagree

17. MANAGEMENT

The explanation given for each of the tools (illustrations) is adequate.

- a. Strongly agree
- b. Agree
- c. Neither agree nor disagree
- d. Disagree
- e. Strongly disagree

18. OTHER TOOLS

I appreciate the fact that it also offers the function of additional links to other tools in each step (Grouping strategies, Available data, ELSEA tools, Communication platform)

- a. Strongly agree
- b. Agree
- c. Neither agree nor disagree
- d. Disagree
- e. Strongly disagree

19. MONITORING AND FEEDBACK

Is under construction.

20. COMMUNICATION PLATFORM

Is under construction.

21. Comments

Comments

7. c: the grading was set at c, because decisions made here are in a black box from a user perspective with no information about consequences

18. c: the "data" aspect is always a little bit hidden. To our needs data are equally important as tools are, and it should be considered to position data equally to tools from a user perspective.

Section 3 – Adequacy

22. The content set (information, tools, links, guides, communication function) fits my needs within my role in the nanotechnology value chain.

- a. Strongly agree
- b. Agree
- c. Neither agree nor disagree
- d. Disagree
- e. Strongly disagree

23. The content of the web-platform (visualization, language, design) is appropriate for my role inside the nanotechnology value chain.

- a. Strongly agree
- b. Agree
- c. Neither agree nor disagree
- d. Disagree
- e. Strongly disagree

24. Comments about the web platform adequacy.

Comments

22. c: we (as training organization in the case study) are not part of the nanotechnology value chain

Section 4 – Usability

25. I find the landing page useful.

- a. Strongly agree
- b. Agree
- c. Neither agree nor disagree
- d. Disagree
- e. Strongly disagree

26. The platform's manual provides sufficient instructions for its profitable use.

(Please, note that the web-platform is not intended to contain concrete instructions on the use of each of the tools, interpretation of data and results, etc.)

- a. Strongly agree
- b. Agree
- c. Neither agree nor disagree
- d. Disagree
- e. Strongly disagree

27. It is easy to learn to use the web platform.

- a. Strongly agree
- b. Agree
- c. Neither agree nor disagree
- d. Disagree
- e. Strongly disagree

28. The menu labels, icons and instructions are clear.

- a. Strongly agree
- b. Agree
- c. Neither agree nor disagree
- d. Disagree
- e. Strongly disagree

29. The movement between screens is simple and intuitive.

- a. Strongly agree
- b. Agree
- c. Neither agree nor disagree
- d. Disagree
- e. Strongly disagree

30. The web-platform has all the necessary links between screens.

- a. Strongly agree
- b. Agree**
- c. Neither agree nor disagree
- d. Disagree
- e. Strongly disagree

31. All the taps, swipes, pinches and scrolls make sense

- a. Strongly agree
- b. Agree**
- c. Neither agree nor disagree
- d. Disagree
- e. Strongly disagree

32. All components and screens are consistent.

- a. Strongly agree
- b. Agree
- c. Neither agree nor disagree**
- d. Disagree
- e. Strongly disagree

33. Other comments about the usability of the web-platform.

Comments
29: b: proposal: if you go back, all further input is lost

Section 5 – Design

34. The layout and size of buttons, icons, menus, and screen content is appropriate.
- a. Strongly agree
 - b. Agree
 - c. Neither agree nor disagree
 - d. Disagree
 - e. Strongly disagree
35. The quality/resolution of the graphics used for the buttons, icons, menus and content is high.
- a. Strongly agree
 - b. Agree
 - c. Neither agree nor disagree
 - d. Disagree
 - e. Strongly disagree
36. The web-platform is visually appealing.
- a. Strongly agree
 - b. Agree
 - c. Neither agree nor disagree
 - d. Disagree
 - e. Strongly disagree
37. Other comments about the design of the web-platform.

Comments

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Section 6 – Personal evaluation

38. The web-platform reflects in an appropriate, coherent, integrated and practical manner the NRGF.

- a. Strongly agree
- b. Agree
- c. Neither agree nor disagree
- d. Disagree
- e. Strongly disagree

39. I would recommend this application to other colleagues who could benefit from it.

- a. Strongly agree
- b. Agree
- c. Neither agree nor disagree
- d. Disagree
- e. Strongly disagree

40. I would use this tool on a regular basis to carry out my risk-related tasks in nanotechnology.

- a. Strongly agree
- b. Agree
- c. Neither agree nor disagree
- d. Disagree
- e. Strongly disagree

41. My overall rating of the application is:

- a. ☆☆☆☆☆
- b. ☆☆☆☆
- c. ☆☆☆
- d. ☆☆
- e. ☆

42. General comments about the web-platform.

Comments

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NANORIGO

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